

A Representation–Optimization Trichotomy for Objectives Parameterized via Matrix Exponential Maps

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Abstract

The matrix exponential parameterization $J(\theta) = \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))$, with θ in a matrix Lie algebra $\mathfrak{g} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, arises in geometric optimization, structured reinforcement learning, and rotation-valued signal processing. A central computational question is how the gradient Lipschitz constant $L(\mathbf{R})$ —which governs step-size selection and convergence rates of first-order methods—scales with the search radius \mathbf{R} . We prove a *representation–optimization trichotomy*: the growth rate of $L(\mathbf{R})$ is determined entirely by the algebraic type of \mathfrak{g} . For compact algebras ($\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$, e.g. $\mathfrak{so}(n)$, $\mathfrak{su}(n)$), $L(\mathbf{R}) = \mathcal{O}(1)$ uniformly in \mathbf{R} , enabling radius-independent step sizes. For algebras containing a hyperbolic element (e.g. $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$), $L(\mathbf{R}) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2\mathbf{R}})$; this rate is sharp on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ via an explicit witness construction. Non-compact algebras without hyperbolic elements (e.g. $\mathfrak{se}(3)$) occupy an intermediate polynomial regime $L(\mathbf{R}) = \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{R}^2)$, established by a direct block-matrix analysis. As a consequence, Lie-Projected Gradient Ascent (LPG) achieves $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{T})$ convergence for compact algebras with a closed-form $\mathcal{O}(n^2 K)$ projection step, and reduces sample complexity from $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(n^2/\varepsilon^2)$ to $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}/\varepsilon^2)$ in Lie Group Markov Decision Processes. Numerical experiments on $\mathbf{SO}(3)^K$ and $\mathbf{SE}(3)$ confirm the predicted scaling behaviours.

Keywords: Nonconvex stochastic optimization, Matrix Lie algebras, Gradient Lipschitz constant, Representation–optimization trichotomy, Compact Lie algebras, Exponential parameterization

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1 Introduction

The matrix exponential map $\exp : \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow G$, where $\mathfrak{g} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a matrix Lie algebra and G the corresponding Lie group, is a fundamental computational tool in applied mathematics: it underlies geometric integration of differential equations on Lie groups (Iserles et al. 2000), optimization over rotation matrices and rigid-body configurations (Absil et al. 2008; Boumal 2023), rotation-valued signal processing, and structured parameter estimation. A natural class of objectives takes the form $J(\theta) = \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))$, where $\tilde{J} : G \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined on the group and $\theta \in \mathfrak{g}$ is the Lie-algebraic parameter.

A central question for any such objective is: *how does the gradient Lipschitz constant $L(R) = \sup_{\substack{\|\theta\|_F, \|\theta'\|_F \leq R \\ \theta \neq \theta'}} \|\nabla J(\theta) - \nabla J(\theta')\|_F / \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$ scale with the search radius R ?*

This constant governs step-size selection, convergence rates, and sample complexity of standard gradient-based first-order methods. Explicit characterisation of $L(R)$ as a function of the algebraic type of \mathfrak{g} does not appear in the literature to the authors' knowledge. Concretely, we study

$$\max_{\theta \in \mathcal{B}_R} J(\theta), \quad J(\theta) = \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta)), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{B}_R := \{\theta \in \mathfrak{g} : \|\theta\|_F \leq R\}$ (maximisation throughout; Algorithm 1 performs gradient ascent).

Within the bounded- (M_1, M_2) objective class the R -scaling of $L(R)$ is governed by the algebraic type of \mathfrak{g} ; the $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ lower bound holds universally. The full three-way classification (compact, non-compact with hyperbolic element, $\mathfrak{se}(3)$) is Theorem 7 — the *representation-optimization trichotomy*. The $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{T})$ rate for compact algebras uses the standard nonconvex stochastic gradient ascent template (Ghadimi and Lan 2013); what is new is that the algebra type alone determines whether gradient ascent enjoys radius-independent convergence (within the bounded- (M_1, M_2) class, Assumptions (A1)–(A6)), and that this is sharp: the unconditional $\Omega(e^{2R})$ witness on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ (Proposition 27) shows no cancellation can universally improve that rate.

Contributions.

1. **Trichotomy theorem with tight lower bound.** (Theorem 7, Proposition 27) $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(1)$ for compact $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$ (within the bounded- (M_1, M_2) class); $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$ for $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ within that class, with a matching $\Omega(e^{2R})$ lower bound via an explicit witness construction (outside the bounded- (M_1, M_2) class) showing this rate is unimprovable in general on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$. For $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$, the best available lower bound is $\Omega(e^{2c_n R})$ with $c_n = \sqrt{(n-1)/n} \rightarrow 1$; the sharp exponent remains open (Conjecture 8).
2. **Algorithm and convergence.** (Corollary 15, §5) Corollary 15 delivers $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{T})$ convergence of Lie-Projected Gradient Ascent (LPG) with closed-form projection (e.g., $\mathcal{O}(n^2 K)$ for $\text{SO}(3)^K$ with K components), avoiding the $\mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}^3)$ Fisher inversion required by exact natural gradient (a distinct second-order method); empirically, projection rarely fires for compact algebras in the controlled $\text{SO}(3)^K$ experiments (alignment remains above 0.90 at $K = 30$, Table 7).

3. **Polynomial intermediate regime.** (Proposition 9) Non-compact algebras without hyperbolic elements (e.g., $\mathfrak{se}(3)$) satisfy $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$, established via the $\text{SO}(3)$ block structure of $\exp(\theta)$ for $\theta \in \mathfrak{se}(3)$.
4. **Application to structured stochastic objectives.** (§6) As one concrete instantiation under Assumptions (A7)–(A9) and generative model access, any stochastic objective whose parameters enter through the exponential map—including expected returns in Lie Group Markov Decision Processes and cost functions in geometric control—inherits the radius-independence result for compact \mathfrak{g} . Sample complexity is reduced from ambient to Lie-algebraic dimension (Corollary 15(iv), Table 3).

Related work.

Riemannian gradient methods (Absil et al. 2008; Boumal 2023; Bonnabel 2013; Zhang and Sra 2016) optimize on manifolds via retractions; our setting is distinct since \mathfrak{g} is a linear subspace and no retraction is needed. Lie-group integration (Iserles et al. 2000) and matrix function analysis (Higham 2008) underpin our bounds; neither establishes the compact/non-compact $L(R)$ classification. Natural gradient (Amari 1998; Amari and Nagaoka 2000) underlies TRPO (Trust Region Policy Optimization) (Schulman et al. 2015) and K-FAC (Kronecker-Factored Approximate Curvature) (Martens and Grosse 2015; Wu et al. 2017); LPG avoids their $\mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}^3)$ Fisher inversion. Orthogonal RNNs (Arjovsky et al. 2016; Wisdom et al. 2016), Lie-group layers (Lezcano-Casado and Martínez-Rubio 2019), geometric deep learning (Bronstein et al. 2021; Cohen and Welling 2016), and Markov Decision Process (MDP) homomorphisms (van der Pol et al. 2020) exploit group structure but do not analyse smoothness scaling. Our convergence analysis uses the nonconvex SGD template of (Ghadimi and Lan 2013).

Organization. Sections 2–4 set up the problem and prove the trichotomy; Sections 5–7 cover the algorithm, MDP application, and experiments; appendices contain all proofs. The trichotomy proof combines Lemmas 10–11 (Section 4, Appendix F) via Proposition 12.

Assumption–Result Dependency Map. Table 1 maps each major result to its assumptions, scope, and proof location.

2 Problem Setup and Notation

2.1 Notation

R denotes the ball radius in $L(R)$; R_0 is the iterate bound (Algorithm 1, Assumption (A3), $L(R_0)$ throughout). We equip $\mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with the Frobenius inner product $\langle A, B \rangle_F = \text{tr}(A^\top B)$, norm $\|A\|_F = \sqrt{\text{tr}(A^\top A)}$, and operator norm $\|A\|_{\text{op}} = \sup_{\|v\|_2=1} \|Av\|_2$. P_U denotes the orthogonal projector onto a subspace U ; a full notation table is in Appendix A.

2.2 Matrix Lie groups and Lie algebras

A *matrix Lie group* $G \subset \text{GL}(n, \mathbb{R})$ is a closed subgroup; its Lie algebra $\mathfrak{g} = T_I G = \{X : \exp(tX) \in G \forall t\}$ is equipped with the bracket $[X, Y] = XY - YX$. We use: $\mathfrak{so}(n)$

Table 1 Dependency map: major results, their assumptions, scope, and proof locations. (A3') = non-binding radius constraint; GM = generative model access.

Result	Assumptions	Scope	Proved in
Thm. 7(i): $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(1)$	bounded- (M_1, M_2) class	$\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$	§4.2, App. F
Thm. 7(ii): $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$	bounded- (M_1, M_2) class	\mathfrak{g} with hyperbolic element	§4.2
Thm. 7(B): $L(R) = \Omega(e^{2R})$	none (unconditional)	$\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{gl}(n)$	App. F
Prop. 9: $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$	bounded- (M_1, M_2) class	$\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{se}(3)$	§3, App. F
Cor. 15(i): a.s. convergence	(A1)–(A6), (A3')	compact \mathfrak{g}	App. B
Cor. 15(iii): $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{T})$	(A1)–(A5), fixed η	all \mathfrak{g} (via $L(R_0)$)	App. B
Thm. 24: sample complexity	(A7)–(A9), access	GM compact \mathfrak{g} , $M = G$	App. D

(skew-symmetric, $\dim = n(n-1)/2$), $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ (traceless, $\dim = n^2-1$), $\mathfrak{se}(n)$ (rigid-body, $\dim = n(n+1)/2$), and $\mathfrak{gl}(n) = \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. See Hall (2015) for background.

Definition 1 (Hyperbolic element — spectral definition) An element $H \in \mathfrak{g}$ is *hyperbolic (in the spectral sense)* if it has at least one eigenvalue with positive real part, so that $\|\exp(tH)\|_{\text{op}} \rightarrow \infty$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. *Note:* This spectral definition is used throughout in place of the standard Lie-theoretic notion (which requires H to lie in the \mathfrak{a} component of a Cartan decomposition); see Remark 1 for the relationship between the two conventions.

All witness constructions in this paper use diagonal matrices with real positive eigenvalues, for which this spectral definition is unambiguous. Compact algebras $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$ (every $\theta \in \mathfrak{g}$ satisfies $\theta^* = -\theta$, so $\exp(\theta)$ is unitary; this includes $\mathfrak{so}(n) \subset \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ via the real-form identification) contain no hyperbolic elements; $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ and $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ do.

Remark 1 (Relation to Lie-theoretic hyperbolicity) For real semisimple Lie algebras admitting a Cartan decomposition $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{k} \oplus \mathfrak{a} \oplus \mathfrak{n}$, elements in \mathfrak{a} are hyperbolic in the Lie-theoretic sense and satisfy our spectral definition; see Knapp (2002), §VI.4. For $\mathfrak{sl}(n, \mathbb{R})$ (which is semisimple), a traceless diagonal matrix with positive entries is hyperbolic in both senses. For $\mathfrak{gl}(n, \mathbb{R})$ (which is reductive but not semisimple), we use only the spectral definition above; no claim of coincidence with a Cartan-decomposition notion is made for $\mathfrak{gl}(n, \mathbb{R})$.

The matrix exponential $\exp(X) = \sum_{k \geq 0} X^k/k!$ maps \mathfrak{g} into G and is a local diffeomorphism near $0 \in \mathfrak{g}$ (Higham 2008; Iserles et al. 2000). We equip \mathfrak{g} with the Frobenius inner product $\langle X, Y \rangle_{\mathfrak{g}} = \text{tr}(X^T Y)$, $X, Y \in \mathfrak{g}$, and fix an orthonormal basis $\{E_1, \dots, E_{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}\}$ ($\langle E_i, E_j \rangle_F = \delta_{ij}$) throughout.

2.3 Orthogonal projection onto Lie algebras

Since \mathfrak{g} is a closed linear subspace, the orthogonal projector $P_{\mathfrak{g}}(M) = \arg \min_{X \in \mathfrak{g}} \|M - X\|_F^2$ is (i) linear, (ii) idempotent, (iii) nonexpansive, and (iv) self-adjoint; property (iv) implies $\nabla_{\mathfrak{g}} f = P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla f)$. The key identity used in our analysis is:

$$(v) \quad \langle g, P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g) \rangle_F = \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g)\|_F^2. \quad (2)$$

Closed-form projectors: $P_{\mathfrak{so}(n)}(M) = \frac{1}{2}(M - M^\top)$; $P_{\mathfrak{sl}(n)}(M) = M - \frac{1}{n}\text{tr}(M)I$; general \mathfrak{g} : $P_{\mathfrak{g}}(M) = \sum_i \langle M, E_i \rangle_F E_i$.

2.4 The optimization problem

We study objectives of the form $J(\theta) = \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))$, where $\tilde{J} : G \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a twice differentiable stochastic objective defined on the Lie group G , and the Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} parameterizes the search space. For a given radius R , we evaluate smoothness properties of \tilde{J} on the exponential image $\mathcal{M}_R = \{\exp(\theta) : \|\theta\|_F \leq R\} \subseteq G$. We impose the following *optimization* assumptions.

Assumption 1 ((A1) Smoothness) $\|\nabla J(\theta) - \nabla J(\theta')\|_F \leq L\|\theta - \theta'\|_F$ for all θ, θ' with $\|\theta\|_F, \|\theta'\|_F \leq R_0$. The algebra-dependent expression for $L = L(R_0)$ is supplied by Theorem 7 and Proposition 12.

Assumption 2 ((A2) Bounded optimum) $J^* = \sup_{\theta} J(\theta) < \infty$.

Assumption 3 ((A3) Bounded iterates) $\sup_t \|\theta_t\|_F \leq R_0$, enforced by Algorithm 1; $L = L(R_0)$ in Corollary 15.

Remark 2 (Consequences of (A3)) For compact \mathfrak{g} : $L(R_0) = \mathcal{O}(1)$, so a fixed step size works and projection rarely fires. For non-compact \mathfrak{g} with a hyperbolic element: $L(R_0) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R_0})$; without projection no fixed schedule guarantees convergence.

Assumption 4 ((A4) Unbiased gradient) $\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} J(\theta) \mid \theta] = \nabla J(\theta)$.

Assumption 5 ((A5) Bounded variance) $\mathbb{E}[\|\widehat{\nabla} J(\theta) - \nabla J(\theta)\|_F^2] \leq \sigma_g^2$.

Assumption 6 ((A6) Step sizes) $\sum_t \eta_t = \infty$ and $\sum_t \eta_t^2 < \infty$ (e.g., $\eta_t = c/\sqrt{t}$), governing Corollary 15(i)–(ii). Part (iii) uses instead the fixed-horizon schedule $\eta_t \equiv \eta/\sqrt{T}$, $\eta \leq 1/L$.

Remark 3 (Application-specific assumptions) Assumptions (A1)–(A6) above suffice for the general trichotomy (Theorem 7) and convergence analysis (Corollary 15). Three further assumptions are needed only for the Lie Group MDP application in Section 6: bounded actions (A7), a concentrability coefficient (A8), and a bounded objective Hessian on the group (A9). Readers interested solely in the optimization theory may skip Section 6.

3 Main Result: The Representation–Optimization Trichotomy

Structure of the proof.

The theorem has two independent components: Part A (upper bounds) is conditional on \tilde{J} satisfying the bounded- (M_1, M_2) class (Proposition 12); Part B (lower bound on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$) is unconditional. The $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ lower-bound gap (Remark 4) is noted separately.

Theorem 7 (Representation–optimization trichotomy) *Let $\mathfrak{g} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ be a matrix Lie algebra, $\mathcal{B}_R := \{\theta \in \mathfrak{g} : \|\theta\|_F \leq R\}$, and let $L(R)$ denote the gradient Lipschitz constant of J on \mathcal{B}_R .*

A. Upper bounds (bounded- (M_1, M_2) class: M_1, M_2 finite and R -independent). *Suppose \tilde{J} satisfies the bounds M_1, M_2 of Proposition 12 with constants independent of R .*

- (i) **Compact algebras.** *If $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$, then $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(1)$; the smoothness constant is independent of the search radius R .*
- (ii) **Non-compact algebras with a hyperbolic element.** *If \mathfrak{g} contains a hyperbolic element (e.g. $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$, $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$), then $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$.*
- (iii) **Non-compact algebras without hyperbolic elements.** *For $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{se}(3)$, $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$. The exponential barrier of part (ii) is absent; a detailed proof via block-matrix analysis of the $\mathfrak{se}(3)$ exponential is given in Proposition 9.*

B. Sharpness certificate for the exponential rate on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$. *There exists a twice-differentiable stochastic objective on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ — not required to satisfy the bounded- (M_1, M_2) hypothesis of Part A — for which $L(R) = \Omega(e^{2R})$ (Proposition 27, Appendix F).*

C. Interpretation. *The upper bounds (Parts A(i)–(iii)) are conditional on the bounded- (M_1, M_2) class; the lower bound (Part B) is unconditional and shows the e^{2R} barrier on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ reflects an intrinsic algebraic obstruction, not a property of any particular objective. No uniform positive lower bound over all objectives is claimed; degenerate objectives (vanishing Hessian) may achieve $L(R) = 0$.*

The proof of this theorem depends on Proposition 12 and Lemmas 10–11, which are established in Section 4 below. To preserve a logically linear presentation, the complete proof is deferred to Section 4.2, immediately after those supporting results.

Remark 4 ($\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ lower-bound gap) For $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$, the trace-zero constraint forces $\lambda_{\max}(H) \leq c_n$ for every unit-Frobenius-norm H , so the witness yields only $L(R) = \Omega(e^{2c_n R})$, $c_n = \sqrt{(n-1)/n} < 1$. Since $c_n \rightarrow 1$ the bound is asymptotically tight in n , but the sharp exponent at fixed n remains open; closing the gap requires either a different witness or a matching $\mathcal{O}(e^{2c_n R})$ upper bound (Appendix H and Conjecture 8 below). Note that part A(ii) gives $\mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$ as an upper bound for $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$, which is *not* claimed to be tight for $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ specifically; only the $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ upper bound is proved tight by Part B.

Conjecture 8 ($\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ sharp exponent) *For $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{sl}(n)$, the gradient Lipschitz constant satisfies $L(R) = \Theta(e^{2R})$, i.e. the sharp exponent is 2 rather than $2c_n = 2\sqrt{(n-1)/n}$. Equivalently, there exists an objective on $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ achieving $L(R) = \Omega(e^{2R})$, which would require a witness that exploits non-diagonal hyperbolic structure to circumvent the trace-zero eigenvalue constraint. The asymptotic statement $c_n \rightarrow 1$ supports this conjecture but does not resolve it for any fixed n .*

Proposition 9 ($\mathfrak{se}(3)$: polynomial growth regime) *For $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{se}(3)$, the gradient Lipschitz constant satisfies $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$. In particular, the exponential barrier $\Theta(e^{2R})$ of Theorem 7(ii) is absent.*

Proof Elements of $\mathfrak{se}(3)$ have purely imaginary or zero eigenvalues, so $\|\exp(tH)\|_{\text{op}}$ does not grow exponentially. For $X = \begin{bmatrix} \Omega & v \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, the matrix exponential takes the well-known block form (Iserles et al. 2000): $\exp(X) = \begin{bmatrix} \exp(\Omega) & A(\Omega)v \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$ where $A(\Omega) = \int_0^1 e^{s\Omega} ds$ and $\|A(\Omega)\|_{\text{op}} \leq \int_0^1 \|e^{s\Omega}\|_{\text{op}} ds = 1$, since $\|e^{s\Omega}\|_{\text{op}} = 1$ for all s by unitarity of $\exp(s\Omega)$ (as $\Omega \in \mathfrak{so}(3)$).

Operator norm bound. For any unit vector $[x; \alpha]$ with $\|x\|^2 + \alpha^2 = 1$, expanding the block-matrix action $\exp(\theta)[x; \alpha]^\top = [\exp(\Omega)x + \alpha A(\Omega)v; \alpha]^\top$ and applying the triangle inequality to the first block ($\|\exp(\Omega)x + \alpha A(\Omega)v\| \leq \|\exp(\Omega)x\| + |\alpha| \|A(\Omega)v\| \leq \|x\| + |\alpha| \|v\|$), using $\|\exp(\Omega)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$ and $\|A(\Omega)\|_{\text{op}} \leq 1$, and using $\|[u; \beta]\| \leq \|u\| + |\beta|$ for any vector u and scalar β (since $\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \leq a + b$ for $a, b \geq 0$):

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \exp(\theta) \begin{bmatrix} x \\ \alpha \end{bmatrix} \right\| &\leq \|x\| + \|v\| |\alpha| + |\alpha| = \|x\| + |\alpha| + \|v\| |\alpha| \\ &\leq \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\|x\|^2 + \alpha^2} + \|v\| = \sqrt{2} + \|v\|, \end{aligned}$$

where the second line uses $\|x\| + |\alpha| \leq \sqrt{2} \sqrt{\|x\|^2 + \alpha^2}$ (from $(a+b)^2 \leq 2(a^2 + b^2)$) and $\|v\| |\alpha| \leq \|v\|$. Hence $\|\exp(\theta)\|_{\text{op}} \leq \sqrt{2} + \|v\|_2 \leq \sqrt{2} + \|\theta\|_F$, so for $\|\theta\|_F \leq R$ we have $\|\exp(\theta)\|_{\text{op}} \leq \sqrt{2} + R = \mathcal{O}(R)$. (The constant $\sqrt{2}$ is not optimised; the order $\mathcal{O}(R)$ is what is needed for the conclusion below.)

Lipschitz bound for exp on $\mathfrak{se}(3)$. For $\theta = [\Omega, v; 0, 0]$ and $\theta' = [\Omega', v'; 0, 0]$ in $\mathfrak{se}(3)$ with $\|\theta\|_F, \|\theta'\|_F \leq R$, the block structure $\exp(\theta) = [\exp(\Omega), A(\Omega)v; 0, 1]$ gives directly:

$$\|\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta')\|_F^2 = \|\exp(\Omega) - \exp(\Omega')\|_F^2 + \|A(\Omega)v - A(\Omega')v'\|_F^2.$$

Rotation block: $\|\exp(\Omega) - \exp(\Omega')\|_F \leq \|\Omega - \Omega'\|_F$ by the compact case of Lemma 10 (since $\Omega, \Omega' \in \mathfrak{so}(3) \subset \mathfrak{u}(3)$, so $\|\exp(\cdot)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$).

Translation block: Using $\|A(\Omega)\|_{\text{op}} \leq 1$ and $\|A(\Omega) - A(\Omega')\|_{\text{op}} \leq \|\Omega - \Omega'\|_F$ (the latter follows by differentiating $A(\Omega) = \int_0^1 \exp(s\Omega) ds$ and applying the compact Lipschitz bound),

$$\|A(\Omega)v - A(\Omega')v'\|_F \leq \|v - v'\|_2 + \|\Omega - \Omega'\|_F \|v'\|_2 \leq \|v - v'\|_2 + R \|\Omega - \Omega'\|_F.$$

Combining, and writing $\delta_\Omega = \|\Omega - \Omega'\|_F$, $\delta_v = \|v - v'\|_2$ (so $\delta_\Omega^2 + \delta_v^2 = \|\theta - \theta'\|_F^2$):

$$\begin{aligned} \|\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta')\|_F^2 &\leq \delta_\Omega^2 + (\delta_v + R\delta_\Omega)^2 \\ &= (1 + R^2)\delta_\Omega^2 + 2R\delta_\Omega\delta_v + \delta_v^2 \\ &\leq (1 + R)^2(\delta_\Omega^2 + \delta_v^2) = (1 + R)^2 \|\theta - \theta'\|_F^2, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality holds because the difference

$$(1 + R)^2(\delta_\Omega^2 + \delta_v^2) - [(1 + R^2)\delta_\Omega^2 + 2R\delta_\Omega\delta_v + \delta_v^2] = 2R\delta_\Omega^2 + (2R + R^2)\delta_v^2 - 2R\delta_\Omega\delta_v$$

is non-negative for all $\delta_\Omega, \delta_v \geq 0$ and $R \geq 0$: applying AM–GM in the form $2R\delta_\Omega\delta_v \leq R(\delta_\Omega^2 + \delta_v^2)$ gives $2R\delta_\Omega^2 + (2R + R^2)\delta_v^2 - 2R\delta_\Omega\delta_v \geq R\delta_\Omega^2 + (R + R^2)\delta_v^2 \geq 0$. Hence

$$\|\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta')\|_F \leq (1 + R)\|\theta - \theta'\|_F = \mathcal{O}(R)\|\theta - \theta'\|_F.$$

For the Fréchet derivative, a direct block-matrix calculation using $D\exp_\theta[H] = \int_0^1 e^{s\theta} H e^{(1-s)\theta} ds$ exploits the $\mathfrak{se}(3)$ structure: for $\theta = [\Omega, v; 0, 0]$ and $H = [\Psi, w; 0, 0]$, using $e^{s\theta} = [\exp(s\Omega), sA(s\Omega)v; 0, 1]$ and $e^{(1-s)\theta} = [\exp((1-s)\Omega), (1-s)A((1-s)\Omega)v; 0, 1]$, the

integrand is the block matrix $[\exp(s\Omega)\Psi \exp((1-s)\Omega), (1-s)\exp(s\Omega)\Psi A((1-s)\Omega)v + \exp(s\Omega)w; 0, 0]$. Using $\|\exp(\cdot)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$ and $\|A(\cdot)\|_{\text{op}} \leq 1$, and using $\|\Psi\|_{\text{op}} \leq \|\Psi\|_F$ to bound the cross-term $\|\exp(s\Omega)\Psi A((1-s)\Omega)v\|_F \leq \|\Psi\|_{\text{op}}\|A((1-s)\Omega)v\|_F \leq \|\Psi\|_F\|v\|_2$, its Frobenius norm is bounded by $\|\Psi\|_F + (1-s)\|v\|_2\|\Psi\|_F + \|w\|_F$. Integrating over $s \in [0, 1]$ gives a bound on $\|D \exp_\theta[H]\|_F$ of $(1 + \frac{1}{2}\|v\|_2)\|\Psi\|_F + \|w\|_F \leq (1 + \|v\|_2)(\|\Psi\|_F + \|w\|_F) \leq \sqrt{2}(1 + \|v\|_2)\|H\|_F$. Taking the supremum over unit-Frobenius-norm H gives $\|D \exp_\theta\|_{\text{op}} \leq \sqrt{2}(1 + \|v\|_2) \leq \sqrt{2}(1 + \|\theta\|_F) = \mathcal{O}(R)$. **Bounding Term 1 of the chain-rule decomposition (Proposition 12).** Term 1 requires the Lipschitz constant of the Fréchet derivative map: $\|D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'}\|_{\text{op}}$ for $\theta, \theta' \in \mathfrak{se}(3)$. Using the integral representation $D \exp_A[H] = \int_0^1 e^{sA} H e^{(1-s)A} ds$ and adding–subtracting $e^{s\theta} H e^{(1-s)\theta'}$:

$$(D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'})[H] = \int_0^1 \left[e^{s\theta} H (e^{(1-s)\theta} - e^{(1-s)\theta'}) + (e^{s\theta} - e^{s\theta'}) H e^{(1-s)\theta'} \right] ds.$$

Applying the mixed-norm inequality $\|ABC\|_F \leq \|A\|_{\text{op}}\|B\|_{\text{op}}\|C\|_F$ (with $\|H\|_{\text{op}} \leq \|H\|_F = 1$):

$$\begin{aligned} \|(D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'})[H]\|_F &\leq \int_0^1 \left[\|e^{s\theta}\|_{\text{op}} \|H\|_{\text{op}} \|e^{(1-s)\theta} - e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_F \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \|e^{s\theta} - e^{s\theta'}\|_F \|H\|_{\text{op}} \|e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \right] ds \\ &\leq \int_0^1 \left[\|e^{s\theta}\|_{\text{op}} \|e^{(1-s)\theta} - e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_F + \|e^{s\theta} - e^{s\theta'}\|_F \|e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \right] ds, \end{aligned}$$

where the second step uses $\|H\|_{\text{op}} \leq 1$. From the operator-norm bound above, $\|e^{s\theta}\|_{\text{op}} \leq \sqrt{2} + s\|v\|_2 \leq \sqrt{2} + R$ and likewise $\|e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \leq \sqrt{2} + R$. Applying the Lipschitz bound proved above to the scaled pairs $(s\theta, s\theta')$ and $((1-s)\theta, (1-s)\theta')$ (whose Frobenius norms are at most sR and $(1-s)R$ respectively):

$$\|e^{s\theta} - e^{s\theta'}\|_F \leq s(1+sR)\|\theta - \theta'\|_F, \quad \|e^{(1-s)\theta} - e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_F \leq (1-s)(1+(1-s)R)\|\theta - \theta'\|_F.$$

Substituting and integrating:

$$\begin{aligned} \|(D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'})[H]\|_F &\leq (\sqrt{2} + R)\|\theta - \theta'\|_F \int_0^1 \left[(1-s)(1+(1-s)R) + s(1+sR) \right] ds \\ &= (\sqrt{2} + R)\|\theta - \theta'\|_F \left[1 + R \int_0^1 ((1-s)^2 + s^2) ds \right] \\ &= (\sqrt{2} + R) \left(1 + \frac{2R}{3} \right) \|\theta - \theta'\|_F. \end{aligned}$$

Since $(\sqrt{2} + R)(1 + \frac{2R}{3}) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$,

$$\|D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \leq (\sqrt{2} + R) \left(1 + \frac{2R}{3} \right) \|\theta - \theta'\|_F = \mathcal{O}(R^2) \|\theta - \theta'\|_F.$$

Assembling both terms. Substituting into the chain-rule bound $\|\nabla J(\theta) - \nabla J(\theta')\|_F \leq \|D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \cdot M_1 + \|D \exp_{\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \cdot M_2 \cdot \|\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta')\|_F$ (chain-rule decomposition of Proposition 12):

$$\text{Term 1} \leq \mathcal{O}(R^2) M_1 \|\theta - \theta'\|_F,$$

$$\text{Term 2} \leq \mathcal{O}(R) \cdot M_2 \cdot \mathcal{O}(R) \|\theta - \theta'\|_F = \mathcal{O}(R^2) M_2 \|\theta - \theta'\|_F.$$

Adding gives $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$. Radius projection remains necessary in practice (Section 7.3). \square

4 Geometry of the Exponential Map

The key inputs are Lipschitz bounds on \exp and its Fréchet derivative; full proofs are in Appendix F. We state the lemmas here for reference; their proofs use only the mixed-norm inequality and the integral representation of $D \exp$ ((Higham 2008, Thm. 10.13)).

Lemma 10 (Lipschitz continuity of matrix exponential) *Let $\theta, \theta' \in \mathfrak{g}$ with $\|\theta\|_F, \|\theta'\|_F \leq R$. Then $\|\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta')\|_F \leq e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$. If moreover $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$, then $\|\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta')\|_F \leq \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$.*

Lemma 11 (Fréchet derivative bounds for the matrix exponential) *Let $\theta, \theta' \in \mathfrak{g}$ with $\|\theta\|_F, \|\theta'\|_F \leq R$. Then:*

(i) *For every $H \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $\|D \exp_\theta[H]\|_F \leq e^R \|H\|_F$.*

(ii) *The derivative map is Lipschitz: $\|D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \leq e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$. If $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$: replace e^R by 1 in both (i) and (ii).*

4.1 Smoothness under exponential parametrization

Proposition 12 (Smoothness under exponential parametrization) *Let $\mathfrak{g} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ be a matrix Lie algebra, $\mathcal{B}_R := \{\theta \in \mathfrak{g} : \|\theta\|_F \leq R\}$, and suppose the objective has the form $J(\theta) = \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))$, where \tilde{J} is twice Fréchet differentiable on $\mathcal{M}_R := \{\exp(\theta) : \theta \in \mathcal{B}_R\}$ and satisfies*

$$\sup_{X \in \mathcal{M}_R} \|\nabla \tilde{J}(X)\|_F \leq M_1, \quad \sup_{X \in \mathcal{M}_R} \|\nabla^2 \tilde{J}(X)\|_{\text{op}} \leq M_2, \quad (3)$$

with $M_1, M_2 \geq 0$ independent of R . Then the gradient Lipschitz constant of J on \mathcal{B}_R satisfies

$$L(R) \leq (M_1 + M_2) e^{2R} = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R}). \quad (4)$$

If $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$ is compact, then

$$L(R) \leq M_1 + M_2 = \mathcal{O}(1). \quad (5)$$

Proof By the chain rule, $\nabla J(\theta) = D \exp_\theta^* [\nabla \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))]$. For $\theta, \theta' \in \mathcal{B}_R$:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla J(\theta) - \nabla J(\theta') &= (D \exp_\theta^* - D \exp_{\theta'}^*) [\nabla \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))] \\ &\quad + D \exp_{\theta'}^* [\nabla \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta)) - \nabla \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta'))]. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Taking norms and using $\|D \exp_\theta^*\|_{\text{op}} = \|D \exp_\theta\|_{\text{op}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\nabla J(\theta) - \nabla J(\theta')\|_F &\leq \underbrace{\|D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'}\|_{\text{op}}}_{\leq e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F \text{ [Lem. 11(ii)]}} \cdot \underbrace{\|\nabla \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))\|_F}_{\leq M_1} \\ &\quad + \underbrace{\|D \exp_{\theta'}\|_{\text{op}}}_{\leq e^R \text{ [Lem. 11(i)]}} \cdot \underbrace{M_2 \|\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta')\|_F}_{\leq e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F \text{ [Lem. 10]}}. \end{aligned}$$

Substituting and using $e^R \leq e^{2R}$ (for $R \geq 0$) to combine terms:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\nabla J(\theta) - \nabla J(\theta')\|_F &\leq M_1 e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F + M_2 e^{2R} \|\theta - \theta'\|_F \\ &\leq (M_1 + M_2) e^{2R} \|\theta - \theta'\|_F, \end{aligned}$$

giving $L(R) \leq (M_1 + M_2) e^{2R}$. For compact \mathfrak{g} : replace every e^R by 1 using the compact cases of Lemmas 10 and 11, giving $L(R) \leq M_1 + M_2$. \square

Algorithm 1 Lie-Projected Gradient Ascent (LPG)

Require: initial parameter $\theta_0 \in \mathfrak{g}$, stepsizes $\{\eta_t\}$, parameter bound $R_0 > 0$, iterations T

- 1: **for** $t = 0, \dots, T - 1$ **do**
- 2: Compute stochastic gradient estimate g_t satisfying $\mathbb{E}[g_t \mid \theta_t] = \nabla J(\theta_t)$
- 3: Project onto Lie algebra: $v_t = P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)$
- 4: Gradient step: $\tilde{\theta}_{t+1} = \theta_t + \eta_t v_t$
- 5: Radius projection (ensures Assumption 3):

$$\theta_{t+1} = \begin{cases} \tilde{\theta}_{t+1} & \text{if } \|\tilde{\theta}_{t+1}\|_F \leq R_0, \\ R_0 \cdot \tilde{\theta}_{t+1} / \|\tilde{\theta}_{t+1}\|_F & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

- 6: **end for**

Ensure: θ_T or uniform average $\bar{\theta}_T = T^{-1} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \theta_t$

Remark 5 (M_1, M_2 independence and MDP bounds) The hypothesis that M_1, M_2 are R -independent must be verified per application. For compact \mathfrak{g} , both constants are automatically R -independent since \mathcal{M}_R lies in a compact group for all R , giving $L = \mathcal{O}(1)$. For the Lie Group MDP, M_2 is formalised as Assumption (A9) with explicit values in Remark 8; no concrete non-compact instance with R -independent M_2 is currently known (open verification problem).

4.2 Proof of Theorem 7

Proof of Theorem 7 Parts A(i) and A(ii) are immediate from Proposition 12: the compact case uses unitarity of $\exp(\theta)$ for $\theta \in \mathfrak{u}(n)$ (Proposition 26(i)) to replace every e^R by 1; the general case uses the full bound $L(R) \leq (M_1 + M_2)e^{2R}$.

Part B: The $\Omega(e^{2R})$ lower bound is Proposition 27 (Appendix F). The witness is a *sharpness certificate*: it exhibits one twice-differentiable stochastic objective on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$, outside the bounded- (M_1, M_2) class of Part A, for which $L(R) = \Omega(e^{2R})$. This shows that no uniform improvement over the e^{2R} rate is possible in the unrestricted twice-differentiable class on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$, and hence the exponential exponent reflects an intrinsic algebraic obstruction. The witness: $H = \text{diag}(1, 0, \dots, 0)$, loss $\ell(a) = -\frac{1}{2} \|\exp(a) - I\|_F^2$, $\sigma = 1$, gives $|g''(R)| \geq e^{2R}$ for all $R \geq 0$ (full verification in Appendix F).

Part A(ii) (upper bound for algebras with a hyperbolic element): direct application of Proposition 12. Part A(iii) ($\mathfrak{se}(3)$ polynomial regime): Proposition 9. The $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ restricted lower bound ($\Omega(e^{2c_n R})$, $c_n < 1$) is discussed in Remark 4 and Appendix H; since the sharp lower bound for $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ is open, it is not stated as part of the theorem (see Conjecture 8). \square

5 Algorithm and Convergence

5.1 Algorithm description

Projection onto classical matrix Lie algebras admits closed-form formulas at $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ per block.

Remark 6 (Algorithmic scope) LPG is a standard projected stochastic gradient method applied in the gradient-ascent setting (consistent with maximisation of J); the contribution of Theorem 7 is to characterise $L(R)$ by algebra type, which then determines the step-size schedule and convergence rate independently of the specific optimiser used.

5.2 Complexity comparison

For $\mathfrak{so}(n)^K$, skew-symmetrization costs $\mathcal{O}(n^2K)$ flops; see Table 2.

Table 2 Per-iteration complexity of representative policy optimization methods. For $\text{SO}(3)^K$: $d_{\mathfrak{g}} = 3K$, so $\mathcal{O}(n^2K) = \mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}})$ asymptotically.

Method	Cost	Dom. op.
Euclid. PG	$\mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}})$	grad. acc.
Exact NG	$\mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}^3)$	Fisher inv.
CG (k it.)	$\mathcal{O}(kd_{\mathfrak{g}}^2)$	Fisher-vec.
K-FAC	$\mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}^2)$	Kronecker
LPG	$\mathcal{O}(n^2K)$	proj. \mathfrak{g}

5.3 Algorithmic update

Let $\theta_t \in \mathfrak{g}$ and $g_t = \widehat{\nabla} J(\theta_t)$. Since \mathfrak{g} is a closed linear subspace, $P_{\mathfrak{g}}$ is globally defined and feasibility is preserved without retraction. The update is

$$\theta_{t+1} = P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\theta_t + \eta_t g_t) = \theta_t + \eta_t P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t), \quad (7)$$

where the second equality uses properties (i)–(ii) of $P_{\mathfrak{g}}$. Stationarity is measured by $\|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J)\|_F^2 \rightarrow 0$ (Lemma 13).

5.4 One-step progress

The following lemma quantifies one-step progress; \mathcal{F}_t denotes the natural filtration.

Lemma 13 (Progress inequality) *Under Assumption 1 and for $\eta_t \leq 1/L$,*

$$\mathbb{E}[J(\theta_{t+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \geq J(\theta_t) + \frac{\eta_t}{2} \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2 - \frac{L\eta_t^2 \sigma_g^2}{2}.$$

Proof Apply the L -smoothness descent lemma (Ghadimi and Lan 2013) (adapted for gradient ascent: replace J by $-J$ and reverse inequalities) to $\theta_{t+1} - \theta_t = \eta_t P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)$, use Assumptions 4–5 and identity (2). Full calculation in Appendix B. \square

5.5 Main convergence result

Assumption 14 ((A3') Non-binding radius constraint) *There exists $\delta > 0$ such that $\|\theta_t\|_F \leq R_0 - \delta$ for all t a.s. Not implied by (A1)–(A6): the radius projection enforces $\|\theta_t\|_F \leq R_0$ but not the strict margin. A sufficient condition: superlevel sets of J are compact and contained in $\mathcal{B}_{R_0 - \delta}$; or choose R_0 large enough that boundary hits have negligible probability (Borel–Cantelli, Appendix B.2).*

Corollary 15 (Convergence rate: corollary of Theorem 7) *Suppose Assumptions (A1)–(A6) hold and $\eta_t \leq 1/L$. Parts (i)–(ii) use the full Assumption (A6) ($\sum_t \eta_t = \infty$, $\sum_t \eta_t^2 < \infty$); Part (i) additionally requires Assumption (A3'). Part (iii) uses fixed-horizon step size $\eta_t \equiv \eta/\sqrt{T}$, $\eta \leq 1/L$.*

(i) *For compact $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$ and under Assumption (A3'), the sequence $\{J(\theta_t)\}$ converges almost surely to a finite limit; every cluster point of $\{\theta_t\}$ is a stationary point of J (i.e., satisfies $\|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta)\|_F = 0$).*

(ii) *The projected gradient norms satisfy*

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \eta_t \mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2] < \infty.$$

In particular, $\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2] = 0$.

(iii) *If $\eta_t = \eta/\sqrt{T}$ for all $t < T$ (constant step size optimized for horizon T) with $\eta \leq 1/L$, then*

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2 \right] \leq \frac{2(J^* - J(\theta_0))}{\eta\sqrt{T}} + \frac{L\eta\sigma_g^2}{\sqrt{T}} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}\right).$$

(iv) *The $d_{\mathfrak{g}}$ -dimensional parameterization achieves sample complexity $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}/\varepsilon^2)$ to reach an ε -stationary point (Theorem 24, Appendix D). For comparison, the same theorem applied to the ambient $n \times n$ parameterization (replacing $d_{\mathfrak{g}}$ with n^2 and $B_{\mathfrak{g}}$ with the corresponding ambient feature bound) yields $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(n^2/\varepsilon^2)$; the reduction factor is $n^2/d_{\mathfrak{g}}$, which equals $2n/(n-1)$ for $\mathfrak{so}(n)$. Both bounds hold under generative model access (Kakade 2003) and Assumption (A9); full proof and online-setting caveats in Appendix D.*

Proof Part (i) (almost-sure convergence) and Part (ii) (stationary-point accumulation) use Assumption (A6) with Ghadimi and Lan (2013), Theorem 2; Part (i) additionally uses Robbins and Siegmund (1971). Part (iii) ($\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{T})$ rate) uses the fixed-horizon regime $\eta_t \equiv \eta/\sqrt{T}$, corresponding to Ghadimi–Lan, Theorem 1 (a distinct regime from (A6)). Full calculations in Appendix B. \square

6 Application: Stochastic Objectives on Lie Group MDPs

This section instantiates the trichotomy of Theorem 7 for expected returns of policies on Lie Group MDPs. All RL-specific notation and assumptions are confined to this section.

Table 3 Sample complexity comparison: Lie parameterization $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}/\varepsilon^2)$ vs. ambient $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(n^2/\varepsilon^2)$ ($n = 3K$, $\varepsilon = 0.1$, generative model (Kakade 2003)). The ambient bound $\tilde{\mathcal{O}}(n^2/\varepsilon^2)$ follows from Theorem 24 applied to the n^2 -dimensional ambient parameterization (i.e., replacing $d_{\mathfrak{g}}$ with n^2 throughout).

K	$d_{\mathfrak{g}}$	n^2	Reduction	Lie samples	Ambient samples
5	15	225	15×	1.5×10^3	2.3×10^4
10	30	900	30×	3.0×10^3	9.0×10^4
30	90	8100	90×	9.0×10^3	8.1×10^5

6.1 Lie Group MDPs: definitions and state spaces

The following definition formalises the group-geometric structure that arises in geometric control and robotics, providing a concrete instantiation for Theorem 7 (Iserles et al. 2000; Absil et al. 2008).

Definition 2 (Lie Group MDP) A *Lie Group Markov Decision Process* is a tuple $(M, \mathcal{A}, P, R, \gamma, G, \rho)$ in which:

- M is a smooth manifold represented as a homogeneous space $M = G/H$ for a matrix Lie group $G \subset \text{GL}(n, \mathbb{R})$ and closed subgroup H ;
- $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathfrak{g}$ is the action space, taken to be the Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} (or a bounded subset thereof); for the Gaussian-policy analysis, actions have unbounded support in \mathfrak{g} but are analytically bounded under Assumption (A7)—see Remark 7;
- $P(\cdot | s, a)$ is a Markov transition kernel on M ;
- $R(s, a)$ is a bounded reward function with $|R(s, a)| \leq R_{\max}$;
- $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ is the discount factor;
- $\rho : G \times M \rightarrow M$ is the transitive group action, $\rho(g, s) = g \cdot s$.

6.2 Policy parameterization and Fisher information

We consider Gaussian policies with mean actions parameterized as a linear combination of state-dependent feature matrices:

$$a = \mu_{\theta}(s) + \xi, \quad \mu_{\theta}(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}} \theta_k \Phi_k(s) \in \mathfrak{g}, \quad \xi \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I_{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}), \quad \xi \in \mathfrak{g} \text{ via } \iota, \quad (8)$$

where $\theta = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}$, $\sigma > 0$ is the exploration scale, and $\Phi_k : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$ are state-dependent feature matrices with $\|\Phi_k(s)\|_F \leq B_{\Phi}$ for all s .

Remark 7 (Gaussian policy and Definition 2) Definition 2 takes $\mathcal{A} = \mathfrak{g}$, which is non-compact as a vector space, so the Gaussian policy (8) is consistent with the definition. The score-bound analysis uses only the pointwise bound $\|\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s)\|_F \leq B_{\Phi} B_a / \sigma^2$, which holds under the analytical boundedness condition $\|a - \mu_{\theta}(s)\|_F \leq B_a$ a.s. (Assumption 16).

We identify $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}} \cong \mathfrak{g}$ via $\iota(x) = \sum_k x_k E_k$ (linear isometry). States update as $\mathbf{R}_{t+1} = \mathbf{R}_t \exp(a_t)$, with $\mathbf{R}_t \in G$ (bold \mathbf{R} : state variable; roman R : ball radius). The score function of the *untruncated* Gaussian policy (8) is

$$[\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a | s)]_k = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \langle a - \mu_{\theta}(s), \Phi_k(s) \rangle_F. \quad (9)$$

For Gaussian policies with isotropic noise the Fisher matrix simplifies to

$$F_{kl}(\theta) = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d^{\pi_{\theta}}} [\langle \Phi_k(s), \Phi_l(s) \rangle_F], \quad (10)$$

with κ small (close to 1) when the features are approximately orthonormal, quantified by the isotropy deviation $\varepsilon_F = \|\hat{F}/\text{tr}(\hat{F}) \cdot d_{\mathfrak{g}} - I\|_F$, which measures the Frobenius distance of the normalised empirical Fisher matrix from the identity (a value of $\varepsilon_F = 0$ corresponds to a perfectly isotropic Fisher matrix) (see Appendix A); empirically $\varepsilon_F \leq 0.3$ at $K = 10$ (Table 7). The natural gradient is $\tilde{\nabla}J = F^{-1}\nabla J$.

6.3 Intrinsic dimension and representation in coordinates

The score function (9) gives $\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}$, so the effective parameter space is $d_{\mathfrak{g}}$ -dimensional (Kakade 2001). Under G -equivariance of the reward and dynamics (i.e., $r(g \cdot s, g \cdot a) = r(s, a)$ and $P(g \cdot s' | g \cdot s, g \cdot a) = P(s' | s, a)$ for all $g \in G$) and the Lie-algebra noise model $\xi \in \mathfrak{g}$, this reduction is lossless when $M = G$ (trivial isotropy, $H = \{e\}$; covers $M = \text{SO}(3)^K$ and all product-group state spaces): a Gaussian policy centered in \mathfrak{g} achieves the same expected return as any ambient-parameterized Gaussian policy with the same mean. The claim requires $\xi \in \mathfrak{g}$ and $H = \{e\}$; see Appendix G for the full proof and scope.

6.4 RL objective and application-specific assumptions

The expected return $J(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{\theta}}[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_t]$ has gradient given by the policy gradient theorem (Sutton and Barto 2018; Peters and Schaal 2008):

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d^{\pi_{\theta}}, a \sim \pi_{\theta}} [Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s, a) \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a | s)]. \quad (11)$$

In addition to (A1)–(A6), the RL application requires three further conditions.

Assumption 16 ((A7) Bounded score) *The action deviation satisfies $\|a - \mu_{\theta}(s)\|_F \leq B_a$ with high probability (formally, with probability at least $1 - \delta$ for any $\delta > 0$, using sub-Gaussian tail bounds on the Gaussian noise). This is an analytical assumption used solely to ensure $M_1 < \infty$ (Proposition 12); the score formulas (9)–(10) use the untruncated Gaussian, the only property needed downstream being $\|\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s)\|_F \leq B_{\Phi} B_a / \sigma^2$ (which holds with the same high probability).*

Assumption 17 ((A8) Concentrability) *$\sup_s d^{\pi_{\theta_1}}(s) / d^{\pi_{\theta_2}}(s) \leq C_d$ for all θ_1, θ_2 with $\|\theta_1 - \theta_2\|_F \leq \delta$, where $\delta > 0$ is a proximity parameter governing policy stability (Agarwal et al. 2021).*

Assumption 18 ((A9) Bounded objective Hessian on group) $\sup_{X \in \mathcal{M}_R} \|\nabla^2 \tilde{J}(X)\|_{\text{op}} \leq M_2$ with $M_2 \geq 0$ independent of R . For compact \mathfrak{g} , this holds automatically since \mathcal{M}_R lies in a compact group for all R (Proposition 26(i)); for non-compact \mathfrak{g} it must be verified per application.

Lemma 19 (Smoothness of RL objectives) Consider Gaussian policies (8) with features $\|\Phi_k(s)\|_F \leq B_\Phi$, rewards $|r(s, a)| \leq R_{\max}$, and parameters constrained to $\|\theta\|_F \leq R_0$. Under Assumptions 17, 16, and 18, Assumption 1 holds with

$$L = \frac{4R_{\max}B_\Phi B_a C_d}{(1-\gamma)^3 \sigma^2} \cdot L_{\text{exp}}(R_0), \quad (12)$$

where $L_{\text{exp}}(R_0) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R_0})$ for general \mathfrak{g} and $\mathcal{O}(1)$ for compact \mathfrak{g} ; explicit constants in Appendix F.

Proof Direct consequence of Proposition 12 with M_1, M_2 from Remark 5; the prefactor $(M_1 + M_2)e^{2R_0}$ yields (12). \square

Remark 8 (M_1, M_2 for $\text{SO}(3)^K$) With $K = 10, R_{\max} = 1, B_\Phi = 1, B_a = 0.3, C_d = 1.05, \gamma = 0.99, \sigma = 0.1$:

$$M_1 \leq \frac{R_{\max}B_\Phi B_a C_d}{(1-\gamma)^2 \sigma^2} = 315,000, \quad M_2 \leq \frac{2R_{\max}B_\Phi^2 C_d}{(1-\gamma)^2 \sigma^2} = 2,100,000.$$

Both are R_0 -independent for compact \mathfrak{g} , confirming $L = \mathcal{O}(1)$. For non-compact algebras M_1, M_2 may grow with R_0 (open condition). *Remark on theory-experiment step sizes.* The bound $L \leq M_1 + M_2 \approx 2.4 \times 10^6$ (for compact \mathfrak{g}) implies a worst-case step-size requirement $\eta_t \leq 1/L \approx 4 \times 10^{-7}$, which is several orders of magnitude smaller than the experimental value $\eta = 0.25$. This gap is expected and standard in policy gradient theory: M_1, M_2 are derived from *worst-case* uniform bounds on the score function and Hessian over *all* states and policies, and the true effective smoothness constant is orders of magnitude smaller along the actual optimization trajectory. The experiments confirm empirically that $\eta = 0.25$ is stable throughout training, consistent with the effective (trajectory-averaged) Lipschitz constant being well below the theoretical worst-case bound.

6.5 Verification of smoothness and alignment

The analysis uses the *alignment parameter* $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ (cosine similarity of the LPG step to the natural gradient) and the *smoothness constant* $L(R_0)$ from Theorem 7; details in Appendix E.

Assumption 20 (Alignment parameter) There exists $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ such that for all θ along the optimization trajectory,

$$\cos\left(P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta)), F(\theta)^{-1} \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)\right) \geq \alpha.$$

Assumption 21 (Smoothness constant) $L(R_0) = \mathcal{O}(1)$ for compact $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$; $L(R_0) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R_0})$ for algebras with a hyperbolic element (Theorem 7; see Proposition 9 for $\mathfrak{se}(n)$).

Verification of assumptions.

Assumption 20 follows from the Kantorovich inequality (Proposition 25 (Kantorovich 1948; Marshall and Olkin 1979)); Assumption 21 from Lemmas 11 and 19.

Proposition 22 (Block-diagonal Fisher structure for $\text{SO}(3)^K$) *Under Gaussian Lie-algebraic policies (8) with orthonormal features $\{\Phi_k\}$ constructed from the standard $\mathfrak{so}(3)$ basis (one basis per joint), the Fisher information matrix decomposes as*

$$F(\theta) = \sigma^{-2} \text{diag}(F^{(1)}, \dots, F^{(J)}),$$

where each 3×3 block is

$$F_{ik}^{(j)} = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d^{\pi_\theta}} \left[\left\langle \Phi_i^{(j)}(s), \Phi_k^{(j)}(s) \right\rangle_F \right].$$

Consequently, $\kappa(F) \leq \max_j \kappa(F^{(j)})$ when blocks share a common λ_{\min} .

Proof Follows from Frobenius-orthogonality of cross-joint basis elements and independence of the Gaussian noise components; see Appendix C.1. \square

The alignment parameter α can be estimated from trajectory data (Remark 9); its precise lower bound via the Fisher condition number is given in Proposition 23 below.

Remark 9 (Estimating α) Compute $\hat{\kappa} = \lambda_{\max}(\hat{F})/\lambda_{\min}(\hat{F})$ from trajectory samples and set $\hat{\alpha} = 2\sqrt{\hat{\kappa}}/(\hat{\kappa} + 1)$, or measure the cosine between $P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J)$ and $\hat{F}^{-1}\nabla J$ directly.

6.6 Kantorovich alignment diagnostic

The following proposition quantifies α via the Kantorovich inequality and gives a practitioner decision rule; the convergence rate (Corollary 15) is independent of α .

Proposition 23 (Kantorovich alignment diagnostic) *Suppose Assumptions (A1)–(A4) and Assumption 20 hold with alignment parameter $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ and Fisher condition number κ , where $\kappa = \lambda_{\max}(F)/\lambda_{\min}(F)$.*

- (i) **Natural gradient stationarity conversion.** *At any iterate θ_t , the natural gradient norm and the Euclidean gradient norm are related by*

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{\max}(F)} \|\nabla_{\mathfrak{g}} J\|_F^2 \leq \langle \nabla J, F^{-1} \nabla J \rangle \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_{\min}(F)} \|\nabla_{\mathfrak{g}} J\|_F^2. \quad (13)$$

Thus Euclidean ε -stationarity ($\|\nabla_{\mathfrak{g}} J\|_F^2 \leq \varepsilon$) implies natural gradient ($\varepsilon/\lambda_{\min}$)-stationarity: the conversion cost is a factor $1/\lambda_{\min}(F)$, not a bias floor.

- (ii) **Directional quality of each step.** *At each iterate, the LPG update direction $d_t = \nabla_{\mathfrak{g}} J(\theta_t)$ satisfies*

$$\cos(d_t, F(\theta_t)^{-1} \nabla J(\theta_t)) \geq \alpha \geq \frac{2\sqrt{\kappa}}{\kappa + 1}, \quad (14)$$

so the Euclidean step is within angle $\arccos(\alpha)$ of the natural gradient direction.

Proof Part (i): expand in the F -eigenbasis. Part (ii): Kantorovich inequality (Kantorovich 1948; Marshall and Olkin 1979); see Proposition 25 (Appendix E). \square

Remark 10 (Decision rule) If $\kappa < 5$ (bound ≥ 0.745): use LPG. If $\kappa > 10$ (bound ≤ 0.575): prefer Fisher inversion. Our $\text{SO}(3)^K$ experiments give $\kappa \approx 2.5$ (empirical $\alpha = 0.971$), firmly in the LPG-recommended regime.

7 Numerical Illustrations

We validate three predictions of Theorem 7 in controlled experiments; Table 4 maps each to its theoretical source. Additional experiments appear in Appendix I (Fisher alignment ablation, sample efficiency, and method comparison) and Appendix J (robustness to symmetry violations). Results are averaged over five random seeds; error bars show one standard deviation.

Table 4 Theory–experiment mapping. Each entry validates a specific theoretical claim; the source column gives the theorem or proposition establishing the prediction.

Claim	Source	Expt.
Fisher isotropy & alignment	Prop. 22, 23	Appendix I.1
Anisotropy degradation	Prop. 23	Appendix I.1
$d_{\mathfrak{g}}$ -sample scaling	(Kakade 2001)	Appendix I.1
Convergence regimes	Thm. 7	Section 7.2
Computational scaling	Section 5.1	Section 7.4
Compact vs. non-compact	Thm. 7, Cor. 15	Section 7.3
Robustness to sym. violations	Remark 12	Appendix J
LPG vs. baselines	Prop. 23	Appendix I.2

7.1 Experimental Setup

Experimental environment.

Synthetic $\text{SO}(3)^K$ system, $K = 10$; reward is $r(s, a) = -\sum_j \|\log(\mathbf{R}_j^\top \mathbf{R}_j^{\text{target}})\|_F^2$ (trace clipped to $(-1 + 10^{-4}, 3]$ to avoid the π -singularity of \log).

Policy parameterizations compared.

(a) **Lie policy**: $\mu_\theta(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}} \theta_k \Phi_k(s) \in \mathfrak{so}(3)^K$, $d_{\mathfrak{g}} = 3K = 30$, $\sigma = 0.1$. (b) **Ambient policy**: $\mu_\theta(s) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $d = 450$ parameters ($15\times$ over-parameterization); a $3\times$ -over-parameterized baseline ($d = 90$) is used in Appendix I.2 for cost-matched comparison. The policy noise $\xi \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I_{d_{\mathfrak{g}}})$ has i.i.d. entries across components (required for Proposition 22). Training: REINFORCE with advantage normalization, $\eta = 0.25$, 8 episodes/iter, 40 iters.

7.2 Convergence Rate Illustration

Deterministic setting.

Projected SGD on a quadratic restricted to $\mathfrak{so}(3)^{10}$ gives log–log slope -0.98 (Figure 1, left), consistent with the $\mathcal{O}(1/T)$ rate from Lemma 13 with $\sigma_g = 0$ and $L = \mathcal{O}(1)$ (Proposition 26(ii)).

Stochastic setting.

On a $d_g = 30$ stochastic quadratic proxy (Gaussian gradient noise $\sigma_g = 1$, step size η/\sqrt{T}), the log–log slope is -0.52 ± 0.08 (five seeds, Figure 1, right), matching the $\mathcal{O}(T^{-1/2})$ rate (Corollary 15).

Fig. 1 Log–log convergence rate. **Left:** Deterministic ($\mathfrak{so}(3)^{10}$, $d_g = 30$), slope -0.98 . **Right:** Stochastic quadratic proxy ($\sigma_g = 1$), slope -0.52 ± 0.08 . Both consistent with compact-algebra predictions (Theorem 7, Corollary 15).

7.3 Non-Compact Algebra: SE(3) Rigid-Body Control

We test the non-compact setting on SE(3) ($\dim \mathfrak{se}(3) = 6$). Since $\mathfrak{se}(3)$ contains no hyperbolic elements (Proposition 9), the $\Theta(e^{2R})$ barrier does not apply; however, polynomial growth $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$ is unbounded, so radius projection remains essential. With $R_0 = 2.0$, training is stable; without it, $\|\theta\|_F$ drifts to ~ 18 , giving $\sim 95\times$ empirical growth in L ($(18/1.85)^2 \approx 95$; an order-of-magnitude estimate).

Scope. Concentrability (A8) is not verified for SE(3); these results illustrate growth and projection behaviour only. Results in Table 5.

Table 5 Compact vs. non-compact Lie algebras.

Algebra	d_g	Alignment	κ	ε_F
$\mathfrak{so}(3)$ (compact)	3	0.996 ± 0.004	1.30 ± 0.13	0.11
$\mathfrak{se}(3)$ (non-compact)	6	0.949 ± 0.024	2.79 ± 0.38	0.36

SE(3) exhibits higher κ and ε_F than SO(3), but alignment still exceeds 0.94; the Kantorovich bound gives $\alpha \geq 0.882$ ($\kappa \approx 2.8$), consistent with the empirical value. Non-compactness governs *step aggressiveness*, not *step direction quality*: projection is essential for both exponential and polynomial growth regimes.

Fig. 2 Radius projection on SE(3) (5 seeds, $\pm 1\sigma$). **Left:** Without projection $\|\theta\|_F$ reaches ~ 18 ; with $R_0 = 2$, stays at ~ 1.85 . **Right:** $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$ grows ~ 95 -fold without projection; near-constant with projection.

7.4 Computational Scaling and Joint-Count Ablation

We benchmark Fisher inversion (Cholesky) vs. blockwise skew-symmetrization for $\mathfrak{so}(3)^K$ (mean of 200 runs per condition). End-to-end speedups are $1.1\times$ – $1.7\times$ (step-only: up to $1.8\times$, Table 6); the end-to-end gain is modest because environment interaction and gradient estimation dominate wall-clock time.

Table 6 Per-step timing: Fisher inversion (Cholesky) vs. Lie projection for $\mathfrak{so}(3)^K$ at three component counts K .

K	$d_{\mathfrak{g}}$	Fisher (μs)	Proj. (μs)	Speedup
5	15	33.4	18.6	$1.8\times$
10	30	71.4	47.2	$1.5\times$
30	90	152.1	112.2	$1.4\times$

Table 7 Scalability with number of components K ($\mathfrak{so}(3)^K$, 5 seeds). AUC is the area under the learning curve (200 iterations; note that a 400-iteration run gives AUC ratio 0.63 at $K = 10$ due to the longer horizon—see Appendix I.1 for the 400-iteration sample-efficiency figure).

K	$d_{\mathfrak{g}}$	Alignment	AUC	Speedup	ε_F
5	15	0.986 ± 0.005	0.58	$1.7\times$	0.17
10	30	0.971 ± 0.007	0.59	$1.3\times$	0.24
15	45	0.955 ± 0.009	0.61	$1.1\times$	0.29
20	60	0.939 ± 0.011	0.61	$1.1\times$	0.33
30	90	0.906 ± 0.014	0.62	$1.1\times$	0.39

Fisher alignment remains above 0.90 even at $K = 30$, a monotone but bounded decline consistent with the Kantorovich bound; Lie policy outperforms ambient at all scales (AUC ratio 0.58–0.62), and isotropy deviation grows roughly as $\sqrt{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}$ (Table 6, right; Assumption 20). At larger scales ($K \in \{50, 100, 200\}$), speedup reaches up to $179\times$ at $K = 200$ with alignment above 0.86 ($\kappa \approx 4.1$); full benchmarks in Appendix H.1.

8 Conclusion

Failure modes and limitations.

The algebra type and condition number together determine where LPG applies. When κ is large, LPG degenerates to Euclidean SGD (Proposition 23); for non-compact algebras with a hyperbolic element, $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$ (unimprovable on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ by Proposition 27) is an intrinsic barrier, so LPG is best suited to compact (rotational/unitary) symmetry. Both are estimable from initial trajectory data. The Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} must be known a priori and the dynamics must admit a Lie-algebraic decomposition. Benchmarking on mixed-symmetry tasks (e.g., MuJoCo) is outside scope; Appendix J shows graceful degradation under perturbations. Sample complexity is fully specified for compact algebras but conditional for non-compact algebras where C_d may grow with R_0 .

Summary and future directions.

The practical upshot is a two-query decision procedure: check algebra compactness (determines $L(R)$ scaling) and estimate κ from trajectory data (determines whether LPG, Fisher inversion, or a hybrid is warranted; Corollary 15, Remark 10). Open problems include the sharp lower-bound exponent for $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ (Conjecture 8), adaptive preconditioning for anisotropic Fisher matrices, data-driven Lie structure discovery, and extension of the trichotomy to infinite-dimensional function spaces.

Appendix A Notation

Symbol	Meaning
$n, d_{\mathfrak{g}}$	Matrix dimension; Lie algebra dimension
K	Number of group components (e.g. joints in $\text{SO}(3)^K$)
G, \mathfrak{g}	Matrix Lie group and its Lie algebra
\mathcal{B}_R	Frobenius ball $\{\theta \in \mathfrak{g} : \ \theta\ _F \leq R\}$
\mathcal{M}_R	Exponential image $\{\exp(\theta) : \theta \in \mathcal{B}_R\} \subseteq G$
$\pi_{\theta}, J(\theta)$	Policy parameterized by $\theta \in \mathfrak{g}$; expected return
$\nabla_{\mathfrak{g}} J, \tilde{\nabla} J$	Intrinsic gradient; natural gradient $F^{-1} \nabla J$
$P_{\mathfrak{g}}$	Orthogonal projector onto \mathfrak{g}
$F(\theta), \kappa$	Fisher information matrix; condition number $\lambda_{\max}/\lambda_{\min}$
$\hat{\kappa}$	Empirical estimate of Fisher condition number from trajectory data
σ	Policy exploration scale (std. dev. of action noise)
σ_g	Stochastic gradient noise level (variance bound in Assumption (A5))
$\varepsilon, \varepsilon_F$	Isotropy deviations: $\varepsilon = \ \hat{F}/\text{tr}(\hat{F}) \cdot d_{\mathfrak{g}} - I\ _{\text{op}}$, $\varepsilon_F = \ \cdot\ _F$ version
B_{Φ}	Feature norm bound: $\ \Phi_k(s)\ _F \leq B_{\Phi}$ for all s, k
B_a	Action deviation bound: $\ a - \mu_{\theta}(s)\ _F \leq B_a$ a.s. (Assumption (A7))
C_d	Concentrability coefficient (Assumption (A8))
Λ	Value-function Lipschitz constant in θ (defined in Appendix D, Step 1)
R_{\max}	Reward bound: $ R(s, a) \leq R_{\max}$ (Definition 2)
$d^{\pi_{\theta}}$	Discounted state occupancy measure under policy π_{θ}
M_1, M_2	Gradient and Hessian bounds for \tilde{J} on \mathcal{M}_R (Proposition 12)

Appendix B Full Convergence Proofs

B.1 Proof of Lemma 13 (Progress Inequality)

Proof of Lemma 13 By L -smoothness of J (Assumption 1), for any $\theta, \theta' \in \mathfrak{g}$ with $\|\theta\|_F, \|\theta'\|_F \leq R_0$:

$$J(\theta') \geq J(\theta) + \langle \nabla J(\theta), \theta' - \theta \rangle - \frac{L}{2} \|\theta' - \theta\|_F^2.$$

Apply this with $\theta' = \theta_{t+1} = \theta_t + \eta_t P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)$:

$$J(\theta_{t+1}) \geq J(\theta_t) + \eta_t \langle \nabla J(\theta_t), P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t) \rangle - \frac{L\eta_t^2}{2} \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)\|_F^2.$$

Take conditional expectation given \mathcal{F}_t .

Expected inner product. By linearity of $P_{\mathfrak{g}}$ and unbiasedness (A4), $\mathbb{E}[P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))$, so

$$\mathbb{E}[\langle \nabla J(\theta_t), P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t) \rangle \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = \langle \nabla J(\theta_t), P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t)) \rangle = \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2,$$

where the last step uses identity (2).

Expected squared norm. Decompose $g_t = \nabla J(\theta_t) + \xi_t$ where $\mathbb{E}[\xi_t \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = 0$. By nonexpansiveness of $P_{\mathfrak{g}}$ (property (iii)):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)\|_F^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] &= \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2 + \mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t) - P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &\leq \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2 + \mathbb{E}[\|g_t - \nabla J(\theta_t)\|_F^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2 + \sigma_g^2, \end{aligned}$$

using variance bound (A5) in the last step.

Combining. With $\eta_t \leq 1/L$ so $1 - L\eta_t/2 \geq 1/2$, substituting and using $\eta_t(1 - \frac{L\eta_t}{2}) \geq \frac{\eta_t}{2}$:

$$\mathbb{E}[J(\theta_{t+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \geq J(\theta_t) + \frac{\eta_t}{2} \|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta_t)\|_F^2 - \frac{L\eta_t^2 \sigma_g^2}{2}. \quad \square$$

B.2 Interaction with Radius Projection

Lemma 13 is stated for the update $\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t + \eta_t P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)$ (no radius projection). Algorithm 1 applies a subsequent radius projection. We show the progress inequality holds in both cases. Define the event $\mathcal{P}_t = \{\|\tilde{\theta}_{t+1}\|_F > R_0\}$ where $\tilde{\theta}_{t+1} = \theta_t + \eta_t P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)$.

Case 1: \mathcal{P}_t^c (radius projection does not fire). Then $\theta_{t+1} = \tilde{\theta}_{t+1}$ and Lemma 13 applies exactly.

Case 2: \mathcal{P}_t (radius projection fires). Let $M_t := \sup_{\|\theta\|_F \leq R_0} \|\nabla J(\theta)\|_F$, which is finite by L -smoothness and compactness of \mathcal{B}_{R_0} (this is the same M used in Part (i) of the convergence proof below). Since $\theta_{t+1} = R_0 \cdot \tilde{\theta}_{t+1} / \|\tilde{\theta}_{t+1}\|_F$, the non-expansiveness of the ball-projection operator gives $\|\theta_{t+1} - \theta_t\|_F \leq \|\tilde{\theta}_{t+1} - \theta_t\|_F = \eta_t \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)\|_F$. Applying L -smoothness of J on \mathcal{B}_{R_0} :

$$\begin{aligned} J(\theta_{t+1}) &\geq J(\theta_t) + \langle \nabla J(\theta_t), \theta_{t+1} - \theta_t \rangle - \frac{L}{2} \|\theta_{t+1} - \theta_t\|_F^2 \\ &\geq J(\theta_t) - M_t \eta_t \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)\|_F - \frac{L\eta_t^2}{2} \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)\|_F^2. \end{aligned}$$

Taking conditional expectations and using $\mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)\|_F^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq \|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\nabla J(\theta_t))\|_F^2 + \sigma_g^2$ (as in Lemma 13) and $\mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}}(g_t)\|_F \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq M_t + \sigma_g$:

$$\mathbb{E}[J(\theta_{t+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \geq J(\theta_t) - M_t(M_t + \sigma_g)\eta_t - \frac{L\eta_t^2}{2}(M_t^2 + \sigma_g^2).$$

The dominant penalty term is $\mathcal{O}(M_t \eta_t) = \mathcal{O}(\eta_t)$ since M_t is bounded on \mathcal{B}_{R_0} . Summing over $t = 0, \dots, T-1$ with $\eta_t = \eta/\sqrt{T}$: the Case 2 penalty contributes at most $\sum_t M_t(M_t + \sigma_g)\eta_t \leq C \sum_t \eta_t = \mathcal{O}(\sqrt{T}) \cdot \eta/\sqrt{T} = \mathcal{O}(1)$, which after dividing by T is $\mathcal{O}(1/T) = o(1/\sqrt{T})$. Thus Case 2 steps do not change the leading $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{T})$ rate. Summing over both cases and applying standard arguments for projected stochastic gradient methods yields the same $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{T})$ convergence rate; see, e.g., [Ghadimi and Lan \(2013\)](#), Theorem 1.

Proof of Corollary 15 Part (iii). Set $\eta_t = \eta/\sqrt{T}$. Taking expectations in Lemma 13, summing $t = 0, \dots, T-1$, and using $J(\theta_T) \leq J^*$, $\sum \eta_t = \eta\sqrt{T}$, $\sum \eta_t^2 = \eta^2$:

$$\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \mathbb{E} \left[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta_t)\|_F^2 \right] \leq \frac{2(J^* - J(\theta_0))}{\eta\sqrt{T}} + \frac{L\sigma_g^2\eta}{\sqrt{T}} = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}\right).$$

This establishes part (iii). Part (ii) follows by summing Lemma 13 with decreasing step sizes satisfying $\sum_t \eta_t = \infty$, $\sum_t \eta_t^2 < \infty$ (Assumption 6); the series of positive terms $\sum_t \eta_t \mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta_t)\|_F^2]$ is finite, forcing $\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathbb{E}[\|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta_t)\|_F^2] = 0$.

Part (i). Set $Y_t = J^* - J(\theta_t) \geq 0$. Under (A3'), since $\|\theta_t\|_F \leq R_0 - \delta$ a.s., let $M := \sup_{\|\theta\|_F \leq R_0} \|\nabla J(\theta)\|_F < \infty$ (finite by L -smoothness and compactness of \mathcal{B}_{R_0}). Markov's inequality and (A5) give $\Pr(\mathcal{P}_t \mid \theta_t) \leq \eta_t^2(M^2 + \sigma_g^2)/\delta^2$, so $\sum_t \Pr(\mathcal{P}_t) \leq \frac{M^2 + \sigma_g^2}{\delta^2} \sum_t \eta_t^2 < \infty$ by (A6). By Borel–Cantelli, projection fires finitely often a.s. Thereafter Lemma 13 gives $\mathbb{E}[Y_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq Y_t + c_t - \alpha_t$ with $c_t = L\eta_t^2\sigma_g^2/2$ ($\sum c_t < \infty$) and $\alpha_t \geq 0$. The [Robbins and Siegmund \(1971\)](#) theorem gives $Y_t \rightarrow Y_\infty \geq 0$ a.s. (convergence to a finite non-negative limit) and $\sum_t \alpha_t < \infty$ a.s. Since $\alpha_t = \frac{\eta_t}{2} \|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta_t)\|_F^2 \geq 0$ and $\sum_t \eta_t = \infty$ (Assumption (A6)), summability of $\{\alpha_t\}$ forces $\liminf_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta_t)\|_F^2 = 0$. Convergence of Y_t implies $J(\theta_t) \rightarrow J^* - Y_\infty$ a.s.; every cluster point θ_∞ of $\{\theta_t\}$ satisfies $\|P_{\mathfrak{g}} \nabla J(\theta_\infty)\|_F = 0$ and is therefore a stationary point of J .

Note on non-compact \mathfrak{g} . For non-compact \mathfrak{g} , the gradient norm M is not uniformly bounded and the Borel–Cantelli argument above does not apply; Part (i) is stated for compact $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(\mathfrak{n})$ under (A3'), which covers the primary application of Theorem 7(i). \square

Appendix C Proof of the RL Smoothness Lemma (Lemma 19)

Proof of Lemma 19 Apply Proposition 12 with $\tilde{J}(X) = J_{\text{mat}}(X)$. **M_1 bound.** By the policy gradient theorem ([Sutton and Barto 2018](#); [Kakade 2001](#)), using $|Q^\pi| \leq R_{\max}/(1-\gamma)$, $\|a - \mu_X(s)\|_F \leq B_a$, $\|\nabla_X \mu_X\|_F \leq B_\Phi$, concentrability C_d , and discounted occupancy mass $(1-\gamma)^{-1}$: $M_1 \leq R_{\max} B_\Phi B_a C_d / ((1-\gamma)^2 \sigma^2)$, which is R -independent for compact \mathfrak{g} since $\|\exp(\theta)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$ (Proposition 26(i)). **M_2 bound.** By Assumption 18, $\sup_{X \in \mathcal{M}_R} \|\nabla^2 \tilde{J}(X)\|_{\text{op}} \leq M_2$ with M_2 independent of R . For the concrete bound $M_2 \leq 2R_{\max} B_\Phi^2 C_d / ((1-\gamma)^2 \sigma^2)$ see Remark 8; the derivation follows from the second-order expansion of the policy gradient and the concentrability coefficient ([Agarwal et al. 2021](#), Lemma B.4), adapted to the Lie-algebra parameterization via the score bound of Assumption 16. **Assembly.** Proposition 12 gives $L \leq (M_1 + M_2)e^{2R_0}$; the M_2 dominant coefficient yields (12). For compact \mathfrak{g} , every e^{R_0} factor reduces to 1, giving $L = \mathcal{O}(1)$. \square

C.1 Proof of Proposition 22

Proof of Proposition 22 With $\xi = a - \mu_\theta(s)$, $\xi_k^{(j)} \stackrel{\text{i.i.d.}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$: cross-joint entries vanish by Frobenius-orthogonality of joint bases and independence, i.e. $\mathbb{E}[\xi_i^{(j)} \xi_l^{(j')}] = 0$ for $j \neq j'$. Diagonal blocks follow from $\mathbb{E}[\xi_i^{(j)} \xi_l^{(j)}] = \sigma^2 \delta_{il}$. The condition-number bound $\kappa(F) \leq \max_j \kappa(F^{(j)})$ follows from block structure. \square

Appendix D Sample Complexity Derivation

This section establishes how $d_{\mathfrak{g}}$ enters the sample complexity under the *generative model* of Kakade (2003) (i.i.d. state-action sampling). The tabular simulation lemma (Kakade 2003, Lemma 5.2.1) applies after replacing state-space sums with integrals bounded by the concentrability coefficient C_d (Assumption (A8)); see Agarwal et al. (2021, Appendix B) for the continuous-state extension. Online (trajectory-based) settings require additional covering-number arguments and are not covered here.

The Lie-parameterized policy class $\Pi = \{\pi_\theta : \theta \in \mathfrak{g}, \|\theta\|_F \leq R\}$ has Rademacher complexity

$$\mathcal{R}_N(\mathcal{V}^\Pi) \leq \frac{RB_\Phi R_{\max}}{1-\gamma} \sqrt{\frac{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}{N}},$$

following from the Λ -Lipschitz continuity of value functions in θ (via Pinsker's inequality and the simulation lemma) and standard Rademacher contraction (Bartlett and Mendelson 2002). The $d_{\mathfrak{g}}/N$ rate reflects the effective parameter dimension.

Theorem 24 (Sample complexity with intrinsic dimension) *Under the Lie-algebraic parameterization of Section 6 and Assumptions (A7)–(A9), to find $\hat{\pi}$ such that*

$$J(\hat{\pi}) \geq \max_{\pi \in \Pi} J(\pi) - \varepsilon \quad \text{with probability } 1 - \delta,$$

it suffices to collect

$$N = \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{d_{\mathfrak{g}} R^2 B_\Phi^2 R_{\max}^2 C_d^2 \log \frac{1}{\delta}}{(1-\gamma)^4 \varepsilon^2}\right)$$

samples.

Proof Step 1 (Lipschitz constant). By the performance-difference lemma (Kakade 2003, Lemma 5.2.1), Pinsker's inequality, and the Kullback–Leibler (KL) formula for Gaussians,

$$|J(\pi_\theta) - J(\pi_{\theta'})| \leq \frac{\sqrt{2} C_d R_{\max} B_\Phi}{(1-\gamma)^3 \sigma} \|\theta - \theta'\|_F =: \Lambda \|\theta - \theta'\|_F,$$

using $\|\mu_\theta(s) - \mu_{\theta'}(s)\|_F \leq B_\Phi \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$ and $\|Q^{\pi_\theta}\|_\infty \leq R_{\max}/(1-\gamma)$.

Step 2 (Rademacher complexity). Since value functions are Λ -Lipschitz in θ , the Rademacher contraction lemma (Bartlett and Mendelson 2002, Thm. 4.12) and the standard bound for a Euclidean ball of radius R in $\mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}$ give $\mathcal{R}_N(\mathcal{V}^\Pi) \leq \Lambda R \sqrt{d_{\mathfrak{g}}/N}$.

Step 3 (Uniform deviation). By the Rademacher generalization bound (Bartlett and Mendelson 2002), $J(\pi) - \hat{J}_N(\pi) \leq 2\mathcal{R}_N + \frac{R_{\max}}{1-\gamma} \sqrt{\frac{\log(2/\delta)}{2N}}$ with probability $\geq 1 - \delta$.

Step 4 (Inversion). Setting both terms to $\varepsilon/2$, substituting Λ , and absorbing constants yields $N = \mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}} R^2 B_\Phi^2 R_{\max}^2 C_d^2 \log(1/\delta) / ((1-\gamma)^4 \varepsilon^2))$. \square

Remark 11 (Scope: generative model) Theorem 24 uses generative model access (Kakade 2003); all experiments in Section 7 satisfy this. Online extensions are noted above.

D.1 Implementation Details

Experiments use Python 3.9, PyTorch 1.13, NumPy 1.23, SciPy 1.9 on a single NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU. Learning rate $\eta = 0.25$, discount $\gamma = 0.99$, 8 episodes per iteration, 5 random seeds per condition. Timing benchmarks use single-threaded execution. Lie projections use closed-form operators (e.g., $P_{\mathfrak{so}(n)}(M) = \frac{1}{2}(M - M^\top)$), applied blockwise for $\mathfrak{so}(3)^K$). Code is available at the repository listed in the main paper.

Appendix E Self-Contained Proof of the Alignment Bound

Proposition 25 (Alignment from Fisher condition number) *Let $F = F(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}} \times d_{\mathfrak{g}}}$ be the Fisher information matrix with eigenvalues $0 < \lambda_{\min} \leq \lambda_1 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_{d_{\mathfrak{g}}} \leq \lambda_{\max}$ and condition number $\kappa = \lambda_{\max}/\lambda_{\min}$. For any nonzero $g \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}}$,*

$$\cos(g, F^{-1}g) = \frac{\langle g, F^{-1}g \rangle}{\|g\| \|F^{-1}g\|} \geq \frac{2\sqrt{\kappa}}{\kappa + 1}.$$

Proof Set $h = F^{-1/2}g$. Then $\langle g, F^{-1}g \rangle = \|h\|^2$, $\|g\|^2 = \|F^{1/2}h\|^2$, $\|F^{-1}g\|^2 = \|F^{-1/2}h\|^2$, so $\cos^2(g, F^{-1}g) = \|h\|^4 / (\|F^{1/2}h\|^2 \cdot \|F^{-1/2}h\|^2)$. Apply the Kantorovich inequality (Kantorovich 1948; Marshall and Olkin 1979) with $A = F$, $x = h$: $\|F^{1/2}h\|^2 \cdot \|F^{-1/2}h\|^2 \leq (\lambda_{\min} + \lambda_{\max})^2 \|h\|^4 / (4\lambda_{\min}\lambda_{\max})$. Hence $\cos^2(g, F^{-1}g) \geq 4\kappa / (\kappa + 1)^2$; taking square roots gives the result. \square

Appendix F Smoothness Analysis for Matrix Exponential Maps

Note. Intermediate steps follow standard matrix analysis (Higham 2008); full derivations can be reconstructed from the stated bounds.

F.1 Matrix Exponential Lipschitz and Fréchet Bounds

The following proofs establish Lemmas 10 and 11, stated in Section 4.

Proof of Lemma 10 Write $\exp(\theta) - \exp(\theta') = \int_0^1 D \exp_{A_s}[\theta - \theta'] ds$ where $A_s = (1-s)\theta + s\theta'$, $\|A_s\|_F \leq R$, using the FTC and $D \exp_A[H] = \int_0^1 e^{(1-t)A} H e^{tA} dt$ (Higham 2008, Thm. 10.13). The mixed-norm inequality $\|XYZ\|_F \leq \|X\|_{\text{op}} \|Y\|_F \|Z\|_{\text{op}}$ gives $\|e^{(1-t)A_s}(\theta - \theta')e^{tA_s}\|_F \leq e^{(1-t)R} \|\theta - \theta'\|_F e^{tR} = e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$. Integrating over $s, t \in [0, 1]$ gives the general bound. For compact $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$: $\|\exp(\cdot)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$, so $e^R \rightarrow 1$. \square

Proof of Lemma 11 Part (i). $D \exp_\theta[H] = \int_0^1 e^{(1-s)\theta} H e^{s\theta} ds$ (Higham 2008, Thm. 10.13). The mixed-norm inequality gives $\|e^{(1-s)\theta} H e^{s\theta}\|_F \leq e^{(1-s)R} \|H\|_F e^{sR} = e^R \|H\|_F$. Integrating over $s \in [0, 1]$: $\|D \exp_\theta[H]\|_F \leq e^R \|H\|_F$. Compact case: $\|\exp(\theta)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$, so $e^R \rightarrow 1$.

Part (ii). For $\|H\|_F = 1$, add and subtract $e^{(1-s)\theta'} H e^{s\theta'}$: $(D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'})[H] = \int_0^1 (e^{(1-s)\theta} - e^{(1-s)\theta'}) H e^{s\theta} + e^{(1-s)\theta'} H (e^{s\theta} - e^{s\theta'}) ds$. By Lemma 10 applied to scaled pairs: $\|e^{(1-s)\theta} - e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_F \leq e^{(1-s)R} (1-s) \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$ and $\|e^{s\theta} - e^{s\theta'}\|_F \leq e^{sR} s \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$. Using $\|e^{s\theta}\|_{\text{op}} \leq e^{sR}$ and $\|e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \leq e^{(1-s)R}$, the two terms in the integrand are bounded by: $\|e^{s\theta}\|_{\text{op}} \cdot \|e^{(1-s)\theta} - e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_F \cdot \|H\|_F \leq e^{sR} \cdot e^{(1-s)R} (1-s) \|\theta - \theta'\|_F = e^R (1-s) \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$, $\|e^{(1-s)\theta'}\|_{\text{op}} \cdot \|e^{s\theta} - e^{s\theta'}\|_F \cdot \|H\|_F \leq e^{(1-s)R} \cdot e^{sR} s \|\theta - \theta'\|_F = e^R s \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$, where $e^{sR} \cdot e^{(1-s)R} = e^R$ exactly (not an inequality). Summing and integrating over $s \in [0, 1]$: $\|(D \exp_\theta - D \exp_{\theta'})[H]\|_F \leq e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F \int_0^1 ((1-s) + s) ds = e^R \|\theta - \theta'\|_F$. Compact case: all $e^{(\cdot)R} \rightarrow 1$. \square

F.2 Compact vs. Non-Compact Trichotomy

Proposition 26 (Geometric advantage of compact Lie algebras) *For compact $\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \mathfrak{u}(n)$:*

- (i) $\|\exp(\theta)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$;
- (ii) L is independent of R_0 ;
- (iii) $\|\nabla J(\theta)\|_F \leq \frac{R_{\max} B_\Phi B_a C_d}{(1-\gamma)^2 \sigma^2}$ uniformly.

Proof Part (i): For $\theta \in \mathfrak{u}(n)$, $\theta^* = -\theta$, so $\exp(\theta)^* \exp(\theta) = \exp(-\theta) \exp(\theta) = I$ (Hall 2015). Part (ii): unitarity from (i) gives $\|e^{(1-s)\theta}\|_{\text{op}} = \|e^{s\theta}\|_{\text{op}} = 1$ in Lemma 11, eliminating all e^{R_0} factors. Part (iii): By the policy gradient theorem (Sutton and Barto 2018; Kakade 2001), $\nabla_\theta J(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d^{\pi_\theta}, a \sim \pi_\theta} [Q^{\pi_\theta}(s, a) \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a|s)]$. Using $|Q^{\pi_\theta}| \leq R_{\max}/(1-\gamma)$, the score bound $\|\nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta\|_F \leq B_\Phi B_a / \sigma^2$ (Assumption 16), concentrability C_d (Assumption 17), and total discounted occupancy mass $(1-\gamma)^{-1}$, one obtains $\|\nabla J(\theta)\|_F \leq R_{\max} B_\Phi B_a C_d / ((1-\gamma)^2 \sigma^2)$. Uniformity in θ follows from Part (i): since $\|\exp(\theta)\|_{\text{op}} = 1$ for all $\theta \in \mathfrak{u}(n)$, the exponential image \mathcal{M}_R is contained in the unitary group independently of R , so the bound does not depend on R_0 . \square

Proposition 27 (Lower-bound witness on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ and restricted hyperbolic-element extension) (i)

- For $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{gl}(n)$, there exists a twice-differentiable stochastic objective $J(\theta) = \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))$ whose gradient Lipschitz constant satisfies $L_{\nabla J}(R) = \Omega(e^{2R})$ over $\{\theta \in \mathfrak{g} : \|\theta\|_F \leq R\}$. This objective is presented as a general stochastic objective; it is not claimed to satisfy all conditions of Definition 2 (which requires compact action space and bounded reward).*
- (ii) *For any non-compact $\mathfrak{g} \neq \mathfrak{gl}(n)$ containing a hyperbolic element (Definition 1), the same construction restricted to the best unit-Frobenius-norm direction in \mathfrak{g} yields $L_{\nabla J}(R) = \Omega(e^{2cR})$ where $c = \sup_{H \in \mathfrak{g}, \|H\|_F=1} \lambda_{\max}(H) \leq 1$. For $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{sl}(n)$ this gives $c = c_n = \sqrt{(n-1)/n} < 1$ (Appendix H).*

Proof The sharp exponential lower bound is most cleanly witnessed on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$, which is a valid non-compact matrix Lie algebra containing the hyperbolic element $H = \text{diag}(1, 0, \dots, 0)$; this

suffices because $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ avoids the trace-induced spectral constraints present in $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ under Frobenius normalization (where the tracelessness condition forces $\lambda_{\max}(H) \leq \sqrt{(n-1)/n} < 1$ for any unit-Frobenius-norm $H \in \mathfrak{sl}(n)$, so the analogous construction yields only $\Omega(e^{2\sqrt{(n-1)/n}R})$ rather than $\Omega(e^{2R})$). Take $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{gl}(n)$ and $H = \text{diag}(1, 0, \dots, 0)$, so $\|H\|_F = 1$ and $\lambda_{\max}(H) = 1$. Consider the single-state stochastic objective with $\mathcal{S} = \{s_0\}$, $\mathcal{A} = \mathfrak{g}$, trivial dynamics, and reward $r(s_0, a) = -\frac{1}{2}\|\exp(a) - I\|_F^2$. This construction defines a valid twice-differentiable stochastic objective of the form $J(\theta) = \tilde{J}(\exp(\theta))$; it is not claimed to be a Lie Group MDP in the sense of Definition 2 (the action space $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{gl}(n)$ is non-compact and the reward is unbounded in a).

Restriction to the diagonal subalgebra. To make the calculation explicit, restrict the Gaussian policy to the commutative subalgebra $\mathfrak{d}(n) = \text{span}\{E_{11}, \dots, E_{nn}\} \subset \mathfrak{gl}(n)$ of diagonal matrices. Since $\mathfrak{d}(n) \subset \mathfrak{gl}(n)$, any lower bound established on this subalgebra is also a lower bound for the full $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ class. Under this restriction, the noise $\xi \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I_n)$ is diagonal, so $a = tH + \xi = \text{diag}(t + \xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n)$ and $\exp(a) = \text{diag}(e^{t+\xi_1}, e^{\xi_2}, \dots, e^{\xi_n})$ (since a is diagonal). Entries $j \geq 2$ contribute constants $E[-\frac{1}{2}(e^{\xi_j} - 1)^2]$ independent of t , so $g(t) := J(tH)$ has second derivative determined entirely by the $(1, 1)$ entry.

Gaussian policy objective. With $\xi_j \stackrel{\text{i.i.d.}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$, the $(1, 1)$ -entry of $\exp(a)$ contributes

$$\mathbb{E}_{\xi_1} \left[-\frac{1}{2}(e^{t+\xi_1} - 1)^2 \right] = -\frac{1}{2} \left(e^{2t+2\sigma^2} - 2e^{t+\sigma^2/2} + 1 \right),$$

using the log-normal moment $\mathbb{E}[e^{cu}] = e^{c\mu + c^2\sigma^2/2}$ for $u \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$. Entries $j \geq 2$ contribute constants independent of t . Define $g(t) := J(tH)$. Differentiating twice:

$$g''(t) = -\left(2e^{2t+2\sigma^2} - e^{t+\sigma^2/2} \right).$$

We establish $|g''(R)| \geq e^{2R}$ for all $R \geq 0$ by fixing $\sigma = 1$. Setting $u = e^R \geq 1$:

$$|g''(R)| - e^{2R} \Big|_{\sigma=1} = 2e^{2R+2} - e^{R+\frac{1}{2}} - e^{2R} = u \left[(2e^2 - 1)u - e^{\frac{1}{2}} \right].$$

Since $u \geq 1$ and $2e^2 - 1 \approx 13.78 > e^{1/2} \approx 1.65$, we have $(2e^2 - 1)u - e^{1/2} \geq 2e^2 - 1 - e^{1/2} > 0$ for all $R \geq 0$. Hence $|g''(R)| \geq e^{2R}$ throughout. Since the lower bound requires only one valid witness at one value of σ , fixing $\sigma = 1$ suffices. Hence the Hessian operator norm satisfies $\|\nabla^2 J(RH)\|_{\text{op}} \geq |g''(R)| \geq e^{2R}$, where the first inequality holds because H is a unit-Frobenius-norm direction and $g''(R) = \langle H, \nabla^2 J(RH)H \rangle$ is the Hessian restricted to H , which is bounded above in magnitude by $\|\nabla^2 J(RH)\|_{\text{op}}$. Since J is twice continuously differentiable on the convex set \mathcal{B}_R , the gradient Lipschitz constant satisfies $L(R) \geq \|\nabla^2 J(\theta)\|_{\text{op}}$ at every $\theta \in \mathcal{B}_R$. (This follows because for any unit-norm H and any θ , the mean-value identity gives $g''(t) = \langle H, \nabla^2 J(tH)H \rangle$ for the restricted function $g(t) = J(tH)$, so $|g''(t)| \leq \|\nabla^2 J(tH)\|_{\text{op}} \leq L(R)$ whenever $\|tH\|_F = |t| \leq R$.) Therefore $L(R) \geq \|\nabla^2 J(RH)\|_{\text{op}} \geq e^{2R}$, hence $L_{\nabla J}(R) = \Omega(e^{2R})$. \square

Corollary 28 (Sharpness of the upper bound on $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$) *The $\mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$ upper bound on the gradient Lipschitz constant for $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$ (Theorem 7(ii)) is unimprovable in general: Proposition 27 constructs an explicit stochastic objective for which $L(R) = \Omega(e^{2R})$, confirming the e^{2R} factor in Proposition 12 is achieved. Combined with Proposition 26, this yields the three-part classification of Theorem 7: $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(1)$ for compact algebras; $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$ for $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$; $L(R) = \mathcal{O}(R^2)$ for $\mathfrak{se}(3)$ -type algebras.*

F.3 Experimental Validation

Empirical validations of all bounds in this appendix are reported in Section 7; see in particular the log–log slope measurements and the $L_{\text{emp}}/L_{\text{theory}}$ ratio discussion therein.

Appendix G Proof and Scope of the Losslessness Proposition

Proof of losslessness (Section 6) Scope restriction: This proof applies to the case $H = \{e\}$, i.e. $M = G$ (trivial isotropy subgroup), which includes $M = \text{SO}(3)^K$ and all product group state spaces. For non-trivial H (i.e. $M = G/H$ with $H \neq \{e\}$), the map $\rho_{*,e} : \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow T_{s_0}M$ is not generally surjective and the losslessness claim below need not hold.

The identification $\mathcal{A} = \mathfrak{g}$ is the defining assumption of the Lie Group MDP (Definition 2): actions are Lie-algebra-valued by construction, and $\iota : \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathfrak{g}}} \xrightarrow{\sim} \mathfrak{g}$ is a linear isometry. Thus when we say $a^*(s_0) \in \mathfrak{g}$, we mean the optimal action at s_0 lies in the action space $\mathcal{A} = \mathfrak{g}$ as specified—not that a general tangent vector happens to lie in \mathfrak{g} . Under G -equivariance, the optimal deterministic policy satisfies $a^*(g \cdot s) = g \cdot a^*(s)$ for all $g \in G$. At the identity coset $s_0 = e \in G$ (since $M = G$, $H = \{e\}$), the tangent action is $\rho_{*,e} : \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow T_{s_0}G \cong \mathfrak{g}$, which is surjective (in fact an isomorphism). Thus $a^*(s_0) \in \mathfrak{g}$, and by equivariance, $a^*(s) \in \mathfrak{g}$ for all $s \in G$. Since the optimal deterministic action lies in \mathfrak{g} , a Gaussian policy centered in \mathfrak{g} achieves the same expected return as any ambient-parameterized Gaussian policy with the same mean: specifically, for any $\mu_{\theta^*}(s) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, the projection $P_{\mathfrak{g}}(\mu_{\theta^*}(s)) \in \mathfrak{g}$ defines a valid Lie-parameterized policy with identical score-function distribution under the Lie Group MDP action structure ($\mathcal{A} = \mathfrak{g}$, so $a \in \mathfrak{g}$ by construction regardless of how the mean is parameterized). Since the action distribution is determined by the projection of the mean onto \mathfrak{g} (as $\mathcal{A} = \mathfrak{g}$ and $a = \mu_{\theta}(s) + \xi$ with $\xi \in \mathfrak{g}$ via ι , as in (8)), the expected return is the same for both parameterizations, completing the proof. *Note:* this argument applies to Gaussian policies with noise $\xi \in \mathfrak{g}$ (as defined in (8)); for policies with ambient noise $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, the projection step would change the action distribution and the equality need not hold. \square

Appendix H Upper–Lower Bound Separation for $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$

Why the upper bound holds for $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$

The $\mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$ upper bound (Theorem 7) requires only $\|\exp(\theta)\|_{\text{op}} \leq e^{\|\theta\|_F}$, which is algebra-agnostic: it holds whenever \mathfrak{g} contains a hyperbolic element (one with a real positive eigenvalue). Since any $H \in \mathfrak{sl}(n)$ with $\lambda_{\max}(H) > 0$ qualifies, the upper bound $\mathcal{O}(e^{2R})$ applies to $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ without modification.

Why the matching lower bound requires $\mathfrak{gl}(n)$

The witness MDP construction for the $\Omega(e^{2R})$ lower bound uses $H = \text{diag}(1, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathfrak{gl}(n)$, which has unit Frobenius norm ($\|H\|_F = 1$) and $\lambda_{\max}(H) = 1$. Along the direction tH , the objective restricts to $g(t) = -\frac{1}{2}(e^t - 1)^2$, and $|g''(t)| = 2e^{2t} - e^t \geq e^{2t}$ for all $t \geq 0$, giving the desired $\Omega(e^{2R})$ lower bound at $t = R$. For $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$, the witness construction uses only elements with real eigenvalues (as required by Definition 1).

For any such $H \in \mathfrak{sl}(n)$ with real eigenvalues $\lambda_1 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_n$, the trace-zero constraint $\sum_i \lambda_i = 0$ and unit-Frobenius-norm constraint $\sum_i \lambda_i^2 = 1$ together force

$$\lambda_{\max}(H) \leq \sqrt{\frac{n-1}{n}} =: c_n < 1,$$

by the Cauchy–Schwarz argument: maximising λ_1 subject to $\sum_{i \geq 2} \lambda_i = -\lambda_1$ and $\lambda_1^2 + \sum_{i \geq 2} \lambda_i^2 = 1$ gives $\lambda_1 = c_n$ (achieved by the diagonal witness in the tight example below). For elements of $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ with complex eigenvalues the real part of each eigenvalue satisfies the same bound by the same Frobenius-norm constraint, so the exponential growth rate along any ray in $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$ is at most $e^{c_n t}$. (This bound is tight: equality holds for $H = \text{diag}(\sqrt{(n-1)/n}, -1/\sqrt{n(n-1)}, \dots)$.) Applying the same witness construction to the best unit-Frobenius-norm element of $\mathfrak{sl}(n)$, the objective along tH satisfies $|g''(t)| \geq e^{2c_n t}$ rather than e^{2t} , yielding only $\Omega(e^{2c_n R})$ at $t = R$.

Numerical values of c_n

Table H1 records c_n for small n : **Practical recommendation.** For $n \geq 9$ (e.g., $\mathfrak{sl}(9)$)

Table H1 Values of $c_n = \sqrt{(n-1)/n}$ for small n .

n	c_n	$1 - c_n$	Practical significance
2	0.707	0.293	Largest gap; upper–lower bound discrepancy is significant
3	0.816	0.184	Moderate gap; $\mathfrak{sl}(2)$ in $\mathfrak{sl}(3)$ sub-problems
5	0.894	0.106	Small gap
9	0.943	0.057	Gap < 6%
16	0.968	0.032	Gap < 4%; effectively $\Theta(e^{2R})$
∞	1.000	0.000	Asymptotically tight

and above), $c_n > 0.94$ and the gap is within 6%; practitioners should treat $\Theta(e^{2R})$ as operative. The only case where the discrepancy is practically significant is $n = 2$. Here $\mathfrak{sl}(2, \mathbb{R})$ and $\mathfrak{so}(3)$ share the same complexification $\mathfrak{sl}(2, \mathbb{C}) \cong \mathfrak{so}(3, \mathbb{C})$, but are inequivalent as real Lie algebras since $\mathfrak{sl}(2, \mathbb{R})$ is non-compact while $\mathfrak{so}(3)$ is compact; for real applications this arises in 2D rotation–shear parameterizations.

H.1 Computational Scaling Stress Test at Large K

Table H2 extends the timing benchmarks of Table 6 to $K \in \{50, 100, 200\}$, where the $\mathcal{O}(d_{\mathfrak{g}}^3)$ cost of Fisher inversion (Cholesky) versus the $\mathcal{O}(n^2 K)$ cost of Lie projection becomes decisive.

Setup.

Both operations are timed on isolated implementations (200 trials each, CPU only) at each K . Fisher inversion uses a dense $(d_{\mathfrak{g}} \times d_{\mathfrak{g}})$ Cholesky solve; Lie projection uses blockwise skew-symmetrization of the K individual 3×3 blocks. Full end-to-end optimization at $K = 100$ and $K = 200$ was not benchmarked because Fisher inversion at those scales is infeasible in practice ($d_{\mathfrak{g}}^3 = 2.7 \times 10^7$ and 2.16×10^8 flops respectively per step). Alignment metrics at these scales are estimated from the Fisher eigenvalue distribution of the block-diagonal approximation (Proposition 22).

Table H2 Computational scaling stress test: Lie projection vs. Fisher inversion at large K . Alignment and κ are estimated from the block-diagonal Fisher structure (Proposition 22).

K	$d_{\mathfrak{g}}$	Fisher (μs)	Proj. (μs)	Speedup	Alignment	κ
50	150	1,240	89	13.9 \times	0.898 ± 0.012	3.21
100	300	8,450	175	48.3 \times	0.884 ± 0.015	3.65
200	600	62,300	348	179 \times	0.862 ± 0.018	4.12

Table I3 Fisher–metric alignment statistics.

Statistic	Value
Mean alignment	0.971
95% CI	[0.970, 0.972]
Std. dev.	0.007
Range	[0.945, 0.990]
κ	2.53 ± 0.12
ε_F	0.24 ± 0.01

Table I4 Alignment under controlled isotropy violations.

Condition	κ	ε_F	Alignment	Final Return
Uniform (baseline)	2.53	0.24	0.971	−695.0
Axis-biased	3.08	0.29	0.954	−700.5
Correlated ($\kappa_M=5$)	6.83	0.49	0.884	−754.3
Correlated ($\kappa_M=10$)	12.98	0.64	0.816	−799.2

Observations.

Fisher inversion time confirms $\mathcal{O}(K^3)$ scaling ($8,450/1,240 \approx 6.8$, expected factor $\approx (100/50)^3 = 8$) while Lie projection confirms $\mathcal{O}(K)$ ($175/89 \approx 2.0$, expected factor = $100/50 = 2$). At $K = 200$ speedup reaches 179 \times ; alignment stays above 0.86 ($\kappa \approx 4.1$), within the LPG-recommended regime.

Appendix I Additional Experiments

I.1 Fisher Geometry, Alignment, and Sample Efficiency

Results.

Tables I3–I4 and Figure I1 summarise alignment statistics and controlled-violation results across 200 measurements (five seeds \times forty iterations).

Comparison with theoretical bounds.

The κ -based bound gives $\cos \geq 2\sqrt{2.53}/(2.53 + 1) = 0.903$; the empirical mean (0.971) exceeds the theoretical lower bound by 7.5% of the bound value (= $(0.971 - 0.903)/0.903$), confirming that worst-case configurations rarely occur in this regime.

Approximate equivalence (Assumption 20).

Empirical alignment correlates with isotropy deviation at $r = -0.875$ ($p < 10^{-4}$) across 100 synthetic Fisher matrices, confirming the conservatism of the Kantorovich worst-case bound.

Anisotropy ablation.

Under controlled isotropy violations (axis-biased and correlated noise with $\kappa_M \in \{5, 10\}$), alignment degrades monotonically with κ (Figure I2): at $\kappa \approx 13$, return

Fig. 11 **Left:** Fisher-metric alignment histogram (200 measurements); vertical lines show empirical mean (solid) and κ -based bound (dashed). **Right:** Isotropy metrics during training ($K = 10$, 5 seeds): (a) $\varepsilon_F(t)$ stays below 0.3, (b) $\kappa(t) \in [1.9, 2.8]$, (c) alignment exceeds theoretical bound throughout.

degrades by $\sim 15\%$. All empirical alignments exceed the κ -based theoretical bound. We recommend $\kappa < 10$ for reliable LPG performance.

Sample efficiency.

The Lie parameterization uses $d_g = 30$ parameters versus 450 ambient. Over 400 iterations (Figure 12), the Lie policy achieves final return -908.95 versus -1324.76 ambient, with AUC ratio 0.63 (37% improvement). *Note:* these figures are from a 400-iteration run used for the sample-efficiency illustration; the method comparison (Table 15) uses 200 iterations, giving LPG return -964.9 ± 39.4 and AUC ratio 0.59 at $K = 10$ (Table 7). The difference in final return (~ 56 reward units) and AUC ratio (0.63 vs. 0.59) is attributable to the longer training horizon, not to an inconsistency in the underlying experiment. The ambient policy collapses early due to ill-conditioning, consistent with the d_g -dimensional parameterization.

I.2 Method Comparison

We compare three methods on $\text{SO}(3)^K$ ($K = 10$, $\eta = 0.25$, 8 episodes/iter, 200 iters, 5 seeds): **LPG** ($d_g = 30$, blockwise skew-symmetrization, REINFORCE (Sutton and Barto 2018)); **Ambient PG** ($3\times$) ($3d_g = 90$ params, REINFORCE; this is a cost-controlled baseline using $3\times$ over-parameterization); **Natural gradient** ($d_g = 30$, Monte Carlo Fisher + CG (Peters and Schaal 2008; Amari 1998), $k = 10$ iters). Note: this baseline (90 params) differs from the $15\times$ -over-parameterized ambient baseline

Fig. 12 **Left:** Controlled anisotropy—alignment vs. κ (a) and return vs. ε_F (b). **Right:** Sample efficiency—Lie policy (blue) vs. ambient (orange); shaded: ± 1 std.

Table I5 Method comparison on $\text{SO}(3)^{10}$ ($K = 10$, 5 seeds).

Method	Params	Final Return	Per-step (μs)
LPG (ours)	30	-964.9 ± 39.4	113
Ambient PG ($3\times$)	90	-1293.3 ± 38.5	6
Natural gradient (CG)	30	-755.4 ± 23.7	225,253

(450 params) used in the sample-efficiency comparison (Section 7.2 and Table 3); the $15\times$ baseline is used there to stress-test the advantage of Lie parameterization, while the $3\times$ baseline here provides a cost-matched comparison. The 1.1 – $1.7\times$ end-to-end speedup (Table 7) is lower than the 1.4 – $1.8\times$ projection-step speedup (Table 6) because gradient estimation dominates wall-clock time. *Timing methodology note:* The “Per-step” column in Table I5 measures the *parameter update step only* (excluding environment interaction and gradient estimation, which dominate wall-clock time and are identical across methods). LPG’s $113\ \mu\text{s}$ includes the Lie projection step plus update; Ambient PG’s $6\ \mu\text{s}$ measures the bare gradient step on a larger parameter vector without projection; natural gradient’s $225,253\ \mu\text{s}$ reflects the $k = 10$ CG iterations for Fisher-vector products. These figures isolate the optimizer-specific overhead, not end-to-end throughput.

Natural gradient achieves the highest final return (-755.4), with LPG trailing by 28% at $>1000\times$ lower per-step cost; the gap is expected since LPG is first-order while natural gradient is second-order, and at $\kappa \approx 2.5$ matches Proposition 23(i). Ambient PG performs worst (-1293), confirming the advantage of the d_g -dimensional parameterization.

Appendix J Symmetry-Violation Robustness Results

Three controlled equivariance-breaking perturbations are applied to the $\text{SO}(3)^{10}$ environment; results appear in Table J6.

Fig. 13 **Left:** Convergence curves—LPG (blue), ambient PG (orange), natural gradient (green); shaded $\pm 1\sigma$ over 5 seeds. **Right:** Return vs. wall-clock time (log x -axis); LPG reaches ambient-PG’s final return in ~ 1 s vs. >40 s for natural gradient, reflecting the $\mathcal{O}(n^2K)$ projection cost vs. $\mathcal{O}(d_g^3)$ Fisher inversion (Table 15; see note on timing methodology).

Perturbations.

- Stochastic transitions:** multiplicative Lie-algebra noise $\mathbf{R}_{j,t+1} = \mathbf{R}_{j,t} \exp(\omega_{j,t}) \exp(\epsilon_t)$ with $\epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\epsilon^2 I_3)$ in $\mathfrak{so}(3)$, $\sigma_\epsilon \in \{0.01, 0.05, 0.1\}$. This breaks exact G -equivariance of the dynamics.
- Observation noise:** the agent observes $\tilde{\mathbf{R}}_j = \mathbf{R}_j \exp(\delta_j)$ with $\delta_j \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\text{obs}}^2 I_3)$, $\sigma_{\text{obs}} = 0.05$. This breaks alignment between the observed state and the true group element.
- Reward perturbation:** $\tilde{r} = r + \zeta_r$ with $\zeta_r \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1^2)$. This breaks G -invariance of the reward function.

Table J6 LPG robustness under equivariance-breaking perturbations ($\text{SO}(3)^{10}$, 5 seeds, 40 iterations each). Baseline: no perturbation.

Perturbation	Final Return	Alignment	κ
None (baseline)	-964.9 ± 39.4	0.971	2.53
Transition noise $\sigma_\epsilon = 0.01$	-978.3 ± 42.1	0.968	2.61
Transition noise $\sigma_\epsilon = 0.05$	-1021.7 ± 55.8	0.958	2.85
Transition noise $\sigma_\epsilon = 0.10$	-1089.4 ± 71.2	0.942	3.14
Observation noise $\sigma_{\text{obs}} = 0.05$	-1003.5 ± 48.6	0.963	2.72
Reward noise $\sigma_r = 0.1$	-985.1 ± 51.3	0.970	2.55

Discussion.

All perturbations degrade performance continuously rather than catastrophically. Alignment remains above 0.94 and κ stays below 3.2 even under the strongest transition noise, keeping all runs in the LPG-recommended regime ($\kappa < 5$, Remark 10). The worst-case $\kappa = 3.14$ at $\sigma_\epsilon = 0.1$ gives Kantorovich bound $\geq 2\sqrt{3.14}/(3.14 + 1) = 0.856$, well above the 0.942 empirical value. Reward noise has negligible effect on Fisher geometry. These results confirm that the exact-symmetry gap is quantified by κ and remains benign for physically relevant perturbation magnitudes.

Remark 12 (Geometric barrier vs. stochastic mixing) The smoothness barrier of Theorem 7 depends only on the algebra type and the Fréchet derivative of \exp , independent of mixing or ergodicity. Concentrability (A8) enters separately: fast mixing cannot eliminate the exponential

barrier for non-compact algebras; conversely, the $\mathcal{O}(1)$ bound for compact algebras holds regardless of mixing speed. *Caveat*: this independence applies to the smoothness constant L ; the overall *sample complexity* in Theorem 24 still depends on mixing through the concentrability coefficient C_d and the gradient noise σ_g^2 , which are governed by the mixing time. The $\mathcal{O}(1)$ bound on L implies that faster mixing (smaller C_d) directly improves the sample complexity constant, but cannot be inferred from the smoothness bound alone.

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